

Women on the Board and Stock Market Performance, Evidence from the Nigerian Listed Firms

Bilyaminu Tijjani¹, Joseph Majiyabo Onyabe², Ahmad Yahaya³
¹Nigerian Airspace Management Agency, Abuja, Nigeria
²Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
³Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria

Received on
05/3/2024
Approved on
27/10/2024

Responsible editor:
Prof. Dr. Daniel Coe

Evaluation process:
Double Blind Review

Abstract

Purpose – This study investigates the impact of female board representation on stock market performance in Nigerian listed firms. Using a sample of 153 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) between 2014 and 2023, we examine the relationship between female board membership and stock returns. This study aims to contribute to the ongoing debate on the role of gender diversity in corporate governance, focusing on the Nigerian context.

Design/methodology/approach – We employ an event study approach, analyzing stock price performances to female board appointments. Regression analysis controls for firm-specific factors, such as size, leverage, and profitability.

Findings – Our results show that female board appointments are associated with significant positive stock market performance. Furthermore, we find that firms with higher female board representation experience improved stock market performance, measured by Tobin's Q.

Originality/value – This study provides novel insights into the Nigerian market, contributing to the scarce literature on gender diversity in Sub-Saharan Africa. Our findings have implications for policymakers, investors, and corporate leaders seeking to promote inclusive governance practices. The key contributions include the first study to examine the stock market performance to female board appointments in Nigeria. First to provide evidence supporting the business case for gender diversity in corporate governance. It informs policy initiatives promoting female representation on boards.

Keywords – Firm Leverage, Firm Liquidity, Firm Size, Nigerian Listed Firms, Stock Market Performances, Women on the Board.

Article QR Code

**Journal of
Accounting and
Finance Education**

DOI: 10.26944/jafe.v10i29.2024

1 Introduction

The poor stock market performance in Nigeria is a multifaceted issue that has attracted significant concern from scholars, regulators, managers, investors, and other stakeholders. The Nigerian Exchange (NGX), now known as the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), has historically faced numerous challenges, some of which stem from economic, political, and regulatory factors, leading to poor performance. Let's break down these concerns and their implications for various stakeholders. For scholars, poor stock market performance provides a rich area for empirical research. It raises questions about the efficacy of existing financial theories in emerging markets like Nigeria. Topics such as market inefficiency, liquidity constraints, corporate governance, and investor behavior become focal points. Poor performance often coincides with inconsistent or poor-quality data, which complicates empirical analysis. This affects the robustness of models and their predictive power, limiting scholars' ability to make definitive conclusions about market behaviour. Nigerian stock market performance has also been linked to corporate governance failures, fraud, and weak regulatory enforcement. Scholars may study these governance issues as case studies to highlight how systemic weaknesses contribute to broader market underperformance.

Regulators such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) of Nigeria are concerned with maintaining market integrity. Poor performance erodes investor confidence, leading to lower participation rates and, ultimately, less capital being available to stimulate economic growth. The lack of confidence may also result in capital flight to more stable markets. A poorly performing stock market reflects badly on the government and its regulatory policies. It raises concerns about the effectiveness of monetary and fiscal policies, the regulatory framework governing the financial markets, and oversight capabilities. The Nigerian government relies heavily on foreign direct investment (FDI) to boost the economy. However, persistent poor stock market performance deters international investors, who perceive the market as too risky. Regulators struggle to enforce policies that balance attracting foreign capital with ensuring domestic stability.

For corporate managers, poor stock market performance translates into difficulties in raising capital. Companies often rely on the stock market for issuing equity to fund expansion and growth. However, when the market underperforms, the cost of raising capital increases, making it less attractive for firms to go public or issue additional shares. Poor performance can also tarnish a company's reputation, leading to increased shareholder pressure. Managers must justify decisions to stakeholders, and declining share prices make it difficult to attract and retain talent, secure favorable lending terms, or execute strategic plans. Weak corporate governance is often cited as a reason for stock market underperformance in Nigeria. Managers face greater scrutiny over transparency, risk management, and financial reporting practices, which can be burdensome in a poorly regulated environment.

Investors are perhaps the most directly affected by poor stock market performance. It leads to a reduction in portfolio value, eroding wealth, and decreasing the incentive to continue investing in the stock market. Retail investors in Nigeria, in particular, may be more sensitive to losses, which results in less participation and liquidity in the market. Poor market performance, combined with cases of market manipulation or corporate fraud, leads to a loss of confidence in the market. Investors may resort to safer asset classes such as real estate or fixed-income securities, reducing the vibrancy of the stock market. Nigerian investors may face challenges in diversifying their portfolios effectively due to limited stock options and high volatility. This reduces their ability to spread risk and achieve stable returns, making the stock market less attractive as an investment vehicle.

The stock market is often seen as a barometer for the economy. Persistent poor performance can be a signal of broader economic challenges, such as weak industrial output, inflation, and unemployment. The stock market's underperformance affects the broader economy by limiting access to finance, thus slowing down growth and job creation. Institutional investors, particularly pension funds, rely on the stock market to generate long-term returns. Poor performance puts pressure on these funds to meet their obligations to retirees, leading to potential liquidity crises or underfunding of pension liabilities. Finally, poor stock market performance erodes public confidence in the financial system. In countries like Nigeria, where financial literacy may be lower, market crashes or downturns can discourage future participation, reducing the likelihood of retail investor growth in the long term.

Some key factors contributing to poor performance include Economic Instability: High inflation, volatile exchange rates, and recessionary pressures have historically affected Nigeria's stock market. Investors fear devaluation of the naira, which reduces their potential returns, especially for foreign investors.

Political Uncertainty: Elections, corruption scandals, and weak governance contribute to stock market volatility. Political instability can cause investor panic, leading to capital flight and stock sell-offs. **Poor Corporate Governance:** Nigerian firms have been criticized for weak corporate governance, lack of transparency, and inadequate risk management. These issues deter investors who seek stable and reliable returns. **Regulatory Inconsistencies:** Regulatory bodies in Nigeria often face criticism for not effectively enforcing market rules, leading to insider trading, market manipulation, and poor corporate disclosures. In conclusion, poor stock market performance in Nigeria is a significant concern for all stakeholders. Scholars are challenged to investigate the underlying causes, develop models, and suggest improvements. Regulators must address systemic weaknesses and create an environment that fosters investor confidence. Corporate managers face increased scrutiny and higher capital costs, while investors experience wealth erosion and reduced diversification opportunities. Ultimately, the poor performance of Nigeria's stock market hinders economic growth, limits job creation, and diminishes public trust in the financial system. Addressing these issues requires coordinated efforts to improve corporate governance, stabilize the economy, and strengthen regulatory frameworks. Only by resolving these deep-rooted challenges can Nigeria's stock market return to sustainable growth and become a more attractive destination for local and international investors.

Furthermore, raising stock market performance in Nigeria is essential to fostering economic growth, attracting both domestic and foreign investments, and enhancing overall market confidence. Addressing the current challenges in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) requires a multi-pronged strategy involving regulatory reforms, market deepening, enhancing investor confidence, and improving corporate governance. Below is an outline of robust strategies that can be employed to raise stock market performance in Nigeria.

Regulatory Reforms and Enhancements; Strengthening the Regulatory Framework: Regulatory bodies like the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Nigerian Stock Exchange must bolster their enforcement mechanisms. By ensuring strict adherence to market regulations, they can reduce instances of insider trading, market manipulation, and fraudulent practices that harm investor confidence. A transparent and predictable regulatory environment promotes fairness and reduces risks for investors.

Improving Market Surveillance: Enhancing market surveillance using advanced technology and data analytics can help detect anomalies, such as suspicious trading activities, early. This proactive approach would discourage market participants from engaging in illicit activities and improve market integrity.

Review of Listing Requirements: Revising the listing requirements to encourage more firms to go public is essential. Streamlining and simplifying these requirements for small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can increase market participation. At the same time, increasing transparency and compliance for large firms can ensure that investors are well-protected.

Effective Dispute Resolution Mechanisms: The establishment of effective dispute resolution mechanisms is crucial in dealing with issues between market participants. Arbitration mechanisms and specialized courts can expedite resolution of conflicts, building investor confidence in the market's legal framework.

Corporate Governance Reforms: Promoting Strong Corporate Governance Standards: Poor corporate governance is a significant factor contributing to stock market underperformance. Companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange should adopt and comply with international best practices in corporate governance. This includes the separation of the roles of CEO and Chairman, transparency in financial reporting, and robust risk management practices.

Strengthening Board Independence: Encouraging gender diversity, skill diversity, and independence on corporate boards can enhance decision-making processes. This also ties into improving board oversight functions and ensuring accountability for corporate management.

Mandatory Audits and Disclosures: Ensuring that firms listed on the exchange undergo regular audits by reputable auditing firms can improve transparency and reduce the risk of financial misreporting. Additionally, mandating more frequent and detailed financial disclosures increases investor trust in corporate data and reduces the chances of shocks from undisclosed financial troubles.

Market Deepening Initiatives: Encouraging More Listings and Initial Public Offerings (IPOs): The Nigerian stock market suffers from a relatively low number of listed companies. The government and the Nigerian Exchange should introduce incentives for more companies to list, including tax breaks, reduced listing fees, and other financial benefits. Encouraging IPOs, especially in growth sectors such as technology, agribusiness, and fintech, can diversify the market and make it more attractive to investors.

Developing New Financial Products: Expanding the range of financial instruments available in the stock market is crucial for deepening the market. This can include introducing Exchange-Traded Funds (ETFs), derivatives like options and futures, and Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs). These instruments offer investors additional avenues for portfolio diversification and hedging, thus increasing market liquidity and overall performance.

Boosting Institutional Participation: Encouraging the participation of

institutional investors such as pension funds, mutual funds, insurance companies, and sovereign wealth funds can enhance market stability and liquidity. Institutional investors typically have long-term investment horizons, which helps mitigate volatility and promotes sustained market growth.

Improving Investor Confidence: Enhancing Investor Education and Awareness: Low financial literacy among retail investors is a significant issue in Nigeria. A concerted effort by regulators, financial institutions, and market stakeholders to improve investor education will help in demystifying stock market investments. Awareness campaigns, investment seminars, and financial literacy programs can help potential investors make informed decisions. **Restoring Confidence through Transparency:** Transparency in trading processes and corporate reporting is critical in restoring and maintaining investor confidence. The Nigerian Exchange should promote full disclosure practices and make it easier for investors to access relevant information about listed companies, their performance, and market dynamics. **Reducing Transaction Costs:** High transaction fees can discourage both local and foreign investors from trading in Nigerian stocks. Reviewing and reducing transaction costs, including brokerage fees, stamp duties, and taxes on securities transactions, will make stock market participation more attractive.

Attracting Foreign Direct Investment (FDI): Improving the Macroeconomic Environment: Stable inflation, currency exchange rates, and interest rates are critical for attracting foreign investors. The Nigerian government, in collaboration with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), must work towards ensuring macroeconomic stability through prudent monetary and fiscal policies. **Liberalizing Capital Controls:** Foreign investors are often deterred by the difficulty of repatriating profits due to capital controls. Liberalizing foreign exchange policies and ensuring investors can easily convert their returns to foreign currencies and repatriate profits will help attract more international capital into the Nigerian market. **Incentives for Foreign Investors:** Offering tax breaks, investment protections, and guarantees on profit repatriation can be instrumental in attracting FDI into Nigeria's stock market. This can be complemented by bilateral agreements with key trading partners that protect foreign investments.

Technological Advancements and Digitalization: Adopting Advanced Trading Platforms: Upgrading the technological infrastructure of the Nigerian Exchange is essential for improving trading efficiency. The adoption of cutting-edge, high-frequency trading platforms and digital channels can reduce transaction times and costs, while increasing the reliability of trades. **Expanding Digital Financial Services:** With the rise of mobile banking and fintech innovations, integrating stock market services with digital platforms will improve accessibility for retail investors. Allowing mobile apps to enable seamless stock purchases, portfolio management, and financial advice can broaden the investor base, especially among younger populations. **Blockchain for Transparency and Security:** Blockchain technology can be leveraged to improve the transparency and security of transactions. Smart contracts could be introduced to ensure automatic and error-free settlements, and blockchain-based records can reduce fraud in trade settlements. **Policy and Structural Reforms: Diversification of the Economy:** Nigeria's stock market is heavily influenced by the performance of the oil sector. Diversifying the economy by promoting sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and technology would reduce the dependence of stock market performance on the volatility of global oil prices. A diversified economy also means a more diversified stock market, reducing risks for investors. **Reducing Bureaucratic Bottlenecks:** Streamlining processes for business registration, tax filing, and regulatory compliance will reduce barriers to entry for companies seeking to list on the exchange. This can also improve the ease of doing business in Nigeria, attracting both local and international firms. **Long-Term Strategic Plans:** The Nigerian government and the NGX should develop a long-term capital market development strategy. This could include policies aimed at increasing market capitalization, improving market depth, and fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors to ensure that the stock market becomes a central vehicle for economic growth.

Sustainable and Responsible Investing: Promoting Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Criteria: Integrating ESG factors into investment decisions is becoming a global trend. Encouraging Nigerian firms to adopt ESG standards and promoting these standards to investors can attract socially responsible investors and increase long-term value creation. **Green Bonds and Sustainable Investments:** The issuance of green bonds and other sustainable investment products can provide an opportunity for companies to raise capital while also promoting environmentally friendly projects. This aligns with global sustainability goals and may attract international investors who prioritize ESG investments. In conclusion, raising stock market performance in Nigeria requires a coordinated approach involving regulatory reforms, corporate governance improvements, technological advancements, and macroeconomic stability. Enhancing transparency, promoting investor education, deepening the market through new products and listings, and encouraging foreign direct investment are all critical strategies. Additionally, aligning with global trends in sustainable investing and leveraging technological innovations can foster long-term growth. If these strategies are implemented effectively, Nigeria's stock

market can become a more dynamic, inclusive, and robust platform that supports economic development and wealth creation.

The role of women on corporate boards has become a critical area of focus in corporate governance research, particularly regarding its potential to improve stock market performance. Numerous studies have suggested that board gender diversity, specifically the inclusion of women in corporate boardrooms, can positively influence company performance and by extension, enhance stock market performance. This section explores, in detail, the role of women on boards in improving stock market performance and highlights various mechanisms through which their presence can contribute to better corporate governance, financial outcomes, and investor confidence.

Enhancing Corporate Governance: Diverse Perspectives in Decision-Making: Women bring different life experiences, skills, and perspectives to board discussions, which can significantly improve the decision-making process. Gender-diverse boards are less prone to groupthink, where decisions are made without sufficient debate or challenge. Women often introduce alternative viewpoints and challenge conventional thinking, encouraging deeper analysis of issues. This improved decision-making can lead to better corporate governance practices, which are linked to stronger firm performance. **Strengthening Ethical Standards:** Studies have suggested that female board members are more likely to adhere to higher ethical standards, which reduces the likelihood of corporate scandals and unethical behavior that could harm a company's reputation and stock price. Women's presence on boards can lead to improved transparency, accountability, and compliance with regulatory frameworks, all of which contribute to better governance and, ultimately, a more stable and attractive stock market performance. **Enhanced Risk Management:** Research indicates that women tend to be more risk-averse than men, making them more likely to adopt cautious and thorough approaches to risk management. In industries where risk-taking needs to be carefully balanced with long-term sustainability, the presence of women on boards can help ensure that risks are managed prudently, preventing excessive risk-taking that can lead to financial instability and stock market volatility.

Improved Financial Performance: Positive Impact on Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE): Empirical research has shown that companies with more women on their boards tend to outperform their counterparts with less gender diversity, particularly in terms of ROA and ROE. These measures of profitability are closely watched by investors, and when they improve, stock prices tend to rise. The belief is that a gender-diverse board brings a range of competencies that drive better financial decision-making, which can translate into higher profitability and stock market returns. **Attracting Long-Term Investors:** Institutional investors, particularly those focused on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors, increasingly favor companies with diverse boards. Many institutional investors see gender diversity as a marker of good governance and sustainability, which aligns with their long-term investment objectives. As a result, companies with more women on their boards may attract more stable, long-term capital from such investors, boosting stock price stability and performance. **Corporate Reputation and Brand Equity:** Companies with gender-diverse boards are often viewed more favorably by the public and stakeholders, which can enhance brand value. A strong corporate reputation often translates into customer loyalty and better financial outcomes, which in turn drives stock market performance. Women's presence on boards can signal to the market that a company is progressive, inclusive, and committed to sustainability—factors that improve investor sentiment and stock valuation. **Enhanced Investor Confidence: Meeting Investor Expectations on Diversity:** Investors are increasingly demanding diversity on boards as part of their broader focus on sustainability and social responsibility. Companies that fail to include women on their boards are viewed as lagging in ESG criteria, which can lead to lower stock valuations. Conversely, companies that prioritize gender diversity align with these investor expectations, which can improve their stock market performance by attracting more responsible and long-term investment. **Reducing Volatility through Governance Stability:** Companies with diverse boards tend to be more stable in their governance structures, which reduces volatility in stock prices. Women on boards contribute to sound corporate governance, which in turn leads to more consistent performance and investor confidence. Stable corporate governance is crucial for minimizing stock price swings, ensuring that stock market performance reflects the intrinsic value of the company rather than being driven by market speculation. **Institutional Investor Support:** Institutional investors are increasingly setting diversity quotas, particularly in developed markets. As Nigeria continues to integrate into global financial markets, domestic companies with women on their boards may gain favor with foreign institutional investors who adhere to these diversity mandates. This can lead to increased capital inflows, greater stock demand, and upward pressure on stock prices.

Mitigating Agency Costs: Improved Board Monitoring: Women tend to enhance the monitoring function of the board, reducing agency costs associated with managerial misconduct or inefficient practices. By

strengthening board oversight, women contribute to better alignment between management and shareholder interests. This alignment ensures that management focuses on maximizing shareholder value, which directly influences stock market performance. Stronger monitoring also reduces the likelihood of financial misreporting or fraud, which could otherwise lead to stock price crashes. Better Compensation and Incentive Structures: Gender-diverse boards are more likely to implement fairer and more balanced executive compensation policies. This reduces the risk of overly generous compensation packages that are not linked to performance, a common source of shareholder dissatisfaction. A well-structured compensation policy aligns executives' interests with the long-term goals of the company, leading to sustainable financial performance that benefits stock market outcomes.

Improving Innovation and Long-Term Strategy: Fostering Innovation through Diversity: Gender-diverse boards are associated with higher levels of innovation. Women often bring new ideas and fresh perspectives, particularly in consumer-facing industries where understanding a broader customer base is critical. This innovation can lead to the development of new products, services, or business strategies that drive revenue growth and improve financial performance, thereby enhancing stock market performance. Better Long-Term Strategic Planning: Boards with women are often seen as being more focused on long-term strategic planning, rather than short-term profit maximization. This is particularly important for stock market performance, as long-term strategic success is a more reliable driver of sustained stock price appreciation than short-term gains. Women on boards may advocate for investments in research and development, human capital, and sustainability, all of which contribute to the long-term health of the company and thus its market valuation.

Positive Impact on Organizational Culture and Employee Satisfaction: Improving Organizational Culture: The presence of women on boards can positively affect a company's culture by promoting inclusivity and diversity at all levels. This creates a more positive work environment, which can increase employee satisfaction and productivity. Companies with strong organizational cultures tend to perform better financially, as engaged employees are more likely to contribute to the company's success. A positive internal culture can attract and retain top talent, which strengthens the company's competitive position and drives better stock performance. Attracting and Retaining Top Talent: Gender-diverse boards signal to potential employees that a company values inclusivity and equal opportunity. This can be a significant competitive advantage in attracting top talent, which in turn drives innovation and performance. Companies with strong human capital tend to outperform their peers, which is reflected in their stock market performance.

Social and Policy Considerations: Government and Regulatory Support for Diversity: In some countries, regulatory bodies and governments have introduced quotas or incentives to promote gender diversity on boards. Nigeria is yet to introduce mandatory quotas, but regulatory bodies can promote gender diversity by offering incentives to companies with diverse boards, such as reduced listing fees or tax incentives. This regulatory support can accelerate the adoption of gender diversity, enhancing corporate governance and stock market performance. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Public Perception: Companies with women on their boards are often seen as being more socially responsible. This has a positive impact on public perception, leading to greater customer loyalty and better corporate reputation. In turn, companies with strong CSR practices are more likely to attract investors who value sustainability and ethical governance, thereby improving stock market performance. In conclusion, the inclusion of women on corporate boards plays a pivotal role in improving stock market performance through several mechanisms. By enhancing corporate governance, contributing to better financial performance, improving investor confidence, reducing agency costs, and fostering innovation, women can make boards more effective and companies more attractive to investors. In a global marketplace where diversity is increasingly valued, companies that prioritize gender diversity on their boards are likely to benefit from better stock performance, both in terms of stability and long-term growth.

In the context of emerging markets like Nigeria, where governance challenges and market inefficiencies persist, the presence of women on boards can signal stronger governance structures and attract both domestic and international capital. Promoting gender diversity at the board level is therefore not just a matter of equity but a strategic move that can enhance the overall performance and competitiveness of Nigeria's stock market. The article is divided into 5 sections. In the next section, a brief review of the literature is carried out. Section 3 describes the sample and the methodology used. Section 4 shows the analysis of the results. Finally, section 5 presents the main conclusions, limitations and suggestions for future research.

2 Literature review

2.1 Stock market performance

Stock market performance refers to the way stock prices and the overall market respond to various events, news,

or changes in a company's performance, macroeconomic conditions, or market sentiment. Stock prices typically reflect investors' collective assessments of these events, adjusting quickly to incorporate new information. A stock market performance can be immediate, gradual, or delayed, depending on the nature and significance of the information, the efficiency of the market, and investor sentiment. Below is a detailed analysis of stock market performances, the factors that influence them, and their implications.

Types of Stock Market Performances:

Positive Performance: When an event or news is perceived as favorable to a company or the market, stock prices rise. Positive performances are usually triggered by strong earnings reports, new product launches, favorable economic policies, or corporate actions like mergers and acquisitions that are expected to increase shareholder value. For instance, if a company reports higher-than-expected profits, its stock price is likely to increase as investors anticipate continued profitability.

Negative Performance: Conversely, when news is interpreted as bad for a company's future performance or the overall economy, stock prices fall. Examples include poor earnings reports, regulatory fines, political instability, or global economic downturns. Negative performances often trigger sell-offs as investors attempt to mitigate their losses.

Neutral Performance: Sometimes, markets do not react significantly to certain events, especially if the news is already priced in or if the market views it as insignificant in terms of future earnings or growth potential. For instance, a routine dividend announcement or slight changes in inflation rates may have little to no impact on stock prices if the market has already anticipated the outcome.

Factors Influencing Stock Market Performances:

Earnings Reports and Financial Performance: One of the most common triggers for stock market performances is the release of a company's quarterly or annual earnings report. If the company beats market expectations, the stock price usually rises (positive performance). If it misses expectations, the stock may fall (negative performance). Other financial metrics like revenue growth, profit margins, and cash flow also influence the magnitude of the performance.

Macroeconomic Data: Changes in interest rates, inflation, unemployment rates, and GDP growth can significantly impact stock market performance. For example, an unexpected interest rate cut by the central bank may lead to a positive stock market performance, as lower interest rates can increase borrowing and stimulate investment. In contrast, rising inflation or unemployment may lead to negative performances due to fears of economic slowdown.

Corporate Actions: Announcements of mergers, acquisitions, stock splits, or share buybacks tend to trigger strong market performances. These actions often signal changes in a company's strategy, capital structure, or future growth prospects. Mergers and acquisitions may lead to price surges if investors believe the deal will create synergies and increase profitability. Similarly, share buybacks are often viewed positively as they reduce the number of shares outstanding and can boost earnings per share.

Market Sentiment and Investor Behavior: Stock market performances are also driven by market sentiment, which refers to the overall attitude of investors toward risk. During periods of optimism (bullish sentiment), markets react positively to even slightly favorable news. Conversely, in periods of pessimism (bearish sentiment), markets may overreact to bad news, leading to larger-than-expected declines in stock prices.

Political and Geopolitical Events: Elections, policy changes, trade disputes, or geopolitical tensions can lead to significant stock market performances. For instance, political instability may trigger a flight to safer assets, leading to stock sell-offs. Conversely, stable political leadership and business-friendly policies tend to support positive stock market performance.

Global Market Trends: Stock markets around the world are interconnected, and significant events in one market can trigger performances in others. For example, a stock market crash in a major economy like the U.S. or China can lead to a ripple effect, causing declines in stock prices across global markets, including emerging markets like Nigeria.

Mechanisms of Stock Market Performances:

Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH): According to the EMH, stock prices reflect all available information, and markets are quick to react to new data. Under this hypothesis, stock market performances occur almost instantaneously when new information is released, leaving little room for arbitrage opportunities. For instance, in an efficient market, positive earnings announcements would lead to immediate price increases, with no delayed performance.

Behavioural Finance: Behavioral finance challenges the EMH by suggesting that investors do not always act rationally. Cognitive biases like overconfidence, herding, and loss aversion can cause investors to overreact or underreact to market events. For example, an overperformance may occur when investors panic after bad news, leading to a larger-than-justified decline in stock prices. Conversely, underperformance may happen if investors are slow to recognize the significance of positive news, leading to gradual price increases over time.

Market Liquidity and Volume: Stock market performances can be more pronounced in markets with low liquidity, where large trades can significantly impact prices. In more liquid markets, large volumes of buy or sell orders are absorbed more efficiently, and performances to news may be less extreme.

Short-Term vs. Long-Term Performances:

Short-Term Performances: Stock market performances are often immediate and short-term, particularly in response to sudden news, such as an earnings report, regulatory change, or geopolitical event. These performances can be volatile as traders attempt to capitalize on price swings. However, short-term performances may not always accurately reflect a company's long-term value.

Long-Term

Performances: Over the long term, stock prices tend to stabilize and align more closely with a company's underlying fundamentals. For instance, a company that consistently delivers strong financial performance will see sustained stock price growth, even if short-term performances to minor events cause temporary volatility. Long-term investors focus on fundamental analysis rather than reacting to short-term noise.

Examples of Stock Market Performances: Positive Performance: Apple Inc.'s stock typically rises after strong quarterly earnings reports. When the company beats expectations on iPhone sales, new product launches, or service revenue growth, investors buy more shares, leading to price increases. Negative Performance: The Volkswagen emissions scandal in 2015 led to a sharp drop in the company's stock price. When it was revealed that the company had used software to cheat emissions tests, investors sold off shares in anticipation of lawsuits, regulatory penalties, and brand damage. Neutral Performance: If a company's earnings report is in line with expectations, there may be no significant stock price movement. For instance, when Alphabet (Google's parent company) reports earnings that meet investor forecasts, the market may not react significantly because the news is already priced into the stock.

Implications for Investors: Short-Term Traders: For short-term traders, stock market performances present opportunities to profit from volatility. By using strategies such as day trading or swing trading, investors attempt to buy stocks ahead of positive performances or sell them before negative performances occur. Long-Term Investors: For long-term investors, stock market performances may be less relevant. These investors focus on fundamental analysis and tend to ignore short-term market noise, instead looking for companies with strong long-term growth prospects. Long-term investors may even view negative short-term performances as buying opportunities if they believe the company's fundamentals remain strong. Risk Management: Understanding stock market performances helps investors manage risk. By anticipating how markets are likely to react to various types of news, investors can adjust their portfolios, hedge against potential losses, or capitalize on opportunities. In conclusion, stock market performances are a natural part of financial markets and reflect the collective responses of investors to new information. These performances can be positive, negative, or neutral, depending on the type of news and market sentiment. Understanding the underlying factors and mechanisms that drive stock market performances—such as corporate performance, macroeconomic conditions, investor sentiment, and global events—enables investors to make informed decisions. In both the short term and the long term, stock market performances provide critical insights into market trends, opportunities, and risks.

Tobin's Q is a financial ratio developed by economist James Tobin to measure a firm's market value relative to its assets' replacement cost. It is widely used as an indicator of stock market performance and corporate governance efficiency. Tobin's Q reflects how effectively a firm's assets are being valued in the stock market, offering insight into whether the market perceives the company as undervalued, fairly valued, or overvalued. In the context of stock market performance, Tobin's Q is especially relevant because it connects stock prices to underlying asset values. If Tobin's Q is greater than 1, it means the market values the firm more than the replacement cost of its assets, suggesting the firm is potentially overvalued or expected to generate future growth. If Tobin's Q is less than 1, it indicates the market values the firm less than the replacement cost of its assets, which may signal undervaluation or inefficiency. Tobin's Q as a Measure of Stock Market Performance: Tobin's Q provides a useful framework for assessing stock market performance because it incorporates both market sentiment (via stock price) and fundamental value (via asset replacement cost). Here are the key reasons why Tobin's Q is used as a measure of stock market performance: Link Between Market Valuation and Real Asset Value: Tobin's Q helps investors assess whether stock prices are supported by the real value of a company's assets. A high Q ratio suggests that the market is pricing in future growth expectations, possibly indicating a bull market. A low Q ratio might suggest that the market is undervaluing companies relative to their real asset base, indicating a bear market or economic inefficiency. Indicator of Overvaluation or Undervaluation: In stock markets, high Tobin's Q ratios may suggest that stock prices are inflated, often leading to speculation of a market bubble. Conversely, low Tobin's Q ratios may indicate undervaluation, presenting buying opportunities for investors who believe the market has mispriced a firm's assets. Corporate Governance and Efficiency: A firm's Tobin's Q can also reflect how well it is governed and how efficiently it uses its assets. Companies with better governance, financial transparency, and effective management practices tend to have higher Tobin's Q ratios, as investors reward these firms with higher market valuations. Thus, Tobin's Q serves as a proxy for assessing a firm's corporate governance effectiveness, which in turn influences stock market performance.

Factors That Influence Tobin's Q: Several factors can affect the Tobin's Q ratio, many of which are directly tied to stock market performance: Stock Market Prices: Since Tobin's Q relies on the market value of a firm, fluctuations in stock prices have a direct impact. Rising stock prices, driven by investor optimism or strong financial performance, increase the numerator of the Tobin's Q equation, driving the ratio higher. Asset Replacement Costs: The denominator in the Tobin's Q ratio is the replacement cost of the firm's assets. If the cost of replacing a company's assets increases, due to inflation or higher input costs, Tobin's Q may decline, even if the firm's market value remains stable. Economic Growth and Investment: In periods of strong economic growth,

companies are generally expected to generate higher returns on assets, leading to higher market valuations and higher Tobin's Q ratios. Conversely, during economic downturns, declining profitability can reduce both stock prices and market valuations, pushing Tobin's Q lower. Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A): M&A activity can significantly affect Tobin's Q. When a firm is acquired at a premium, its market value spikes, driving Tobin's Q higher. Similarly, a firm engaged in a value-adding acquisition may see its Q ratio rise as market participants price in the potential benefits of the acquisition. Intangible Assets: Tobin's Q tends to be higher for firms with substantial intangible assets such as brand reputation, intellectual property, and patents. These assets are often not reflected in the replacement cost but significantly contribute to a firm's market value.

Interpretation of Tobin's Q in Stock Market Context: $Q > 1$ (Overvaluation): A Tobin's Q greater than 1 indicates that the market value of a firm exceeds the replacement cost of its assets. This often signals that investors are optimistic about the company's future profitability and growth potential. However, it could also suggest overvaluation if the market has inflated the stock price beyond the company's intrinsic value. Stock Market Implication: A high Tobin's Q may indicate a speculative market environment, where investors are pricing in future growth expectations. If these expectations are not met, stock prices could correct sharply, leading to market volatility or even a market crash. $Q < 1$ (Undervaluation): A Tobin's Q less than 1 suggests that the market values the firm less than the cost of its assets. This may indicate that the firm is undervalued by the market, presenting a potential opportunity for investors. It may also imply poor market conditions or inefficiencies in the firm's operations. Stock Market Implication: A low Tobin's Q could suggest a bearish market, where stocks are undervalued due to economic downturns or low investor confidence. For value investors, this presents an opportunity to buy undervalued stocks at a discount, with the potential for long-term gains.

Use of Tobin's Q in Emerging Markets: In emerging markets like Nigeria, Tobin's Q can be particularly useful for analyzing the efficiency and performance of companies listed on the stock exchange. Given that emerging markets often face volatility, inefficiency, and governance issues, Tobin's Q helps assess whether firms are being over- or undervalued relative to their assets. Corporate Governance in Nigeria: Tobin's Q can serve as a benchmark for evaluating corporate governance in Nigerian firms. Companies with higher Q ratios may be better governed, making them more attractive to foreign investors looking for well-run companies. On the other hand, firms with low Q ratios may be undervalued due to governance challenges or market inefficiencies, offering turnaround potential if governance improves. Stock Market Performance in Nigeria: Given the volatility in Nigeria's stock market and its sensitivity to macroeconomic factors like oil prices and exchange rate fluctuations, Tobin's Q can help investors differentiate between temporary market distortions and long-term value. For instance, during periods of economic crisis, Tobin's Q ratios may fall as asset values exceed market prices, presenting buying opportunities for value-oriented investors.

Limitations of Tobin's Q: Difficulty in Estimating Replacement Cost: One challenge with Tobin's Q is estimating the replacement cost of a firm's assets. This can be especially difficult for companies with a significant portion of intangible assets, as these are hard to value accurately. As a result, Tobin's Q may not always provide a precise measure of a company's value. Market Bubbles: In periods of speculative bubbles, Tobin's Q can rise significantly above 1, reflecting excessive market optimism rather than true value. This may lead to misleading conclusions about the firm's actual performance and future prospects. Relevance Across Sectors: Tobin's Q may be less relevant in sectors where the replacement cost of assets is difficult to calculate or in industries where asset-light business models (e.g., technology or services) dominate. In such cases, market value may diverge significantly from asset values. In conclusion, Tobin's Q is a valuable tool for assessing stock market performance, as it links a firm's market value with the replacement cost of its assets. A higher Q ratio indicates that the market values the firm above its asset base, which can signal investor optimism or overvaluation. Conversely, a lower Q ratio suggests undervaluation, providing potential investment opportunities. Tobin's Q is particularly useful in emerging markets like Nigeria, where it can highlight inefficiencies, corporate governance issues, or mispricings. However, it also has limitations, especially in accurately measuring intangible assets and during speculative market periods. The presence of women on corporate boards has become a key focus in discussions about corporate governance, diversity, and organizational performance. Over the past few decades, many countries and organizations have made concerted efforts to increase the representation of women on boards, driven by the belief that gender diversity leads to better decision-making, improved corporate governance, and enhanced financial performance. Numerous studies suggest that having women on corporate boards can positively impact the company's culture, innovation, and reputation while improving its financial and non-financial outcomes. The Importance of Women on Corporate Boards: Diversity of Thought: Women bring different perspectives, experiences, and skills to corporate boards, which enhances the decision-making process. Gender-diverse boards are better equipped to avoid "groupthink"—a situation where homogeneous groups make suboptimal decisions due to a lack of dissenting opinions or diverse viewpoints. Women often prioritize collaboration, consensus-building, and holistic decision-making, which can lead to more thoughtful and balanced boardroom discussions. Corporate Governance: Having women on corporate boards improves governance by fostering greater accountability and transparency. Women directors tend to focus

more on ethics, risk management, and long-term sustainability, which aligns with good governance practices. Studies have shown that boards with female representation are more likely to oversee comprehensive risk assessments and promote ethical behavior, helping to build trust with stakeholders. Reputation and Stakeholder Engagement: Companies with diverse boards often enjoy stronger reputations among investors, consumers, and employees. In an era where stakeholders value corporate social responsibility (CSR) and diversity, a board that reflects gender inclusivity signals that the company is committed to these principles. This can attract a broader base of investors and enhance the company's market positioning. Talent Development and Retention: Companies with women on their boards are seen as more inclusive and equitable. This can boost employee morale, attract top talent, and create a pipeline of female leaders within the organization. A more inclusive workplace culture can also enhance employee retention, leading to lower turnover costs and a more committed workforce.

Impact of Women on Corporate Boards on Financial Performance: The relationship between gender diversity on boards and financial performance has been widely studied, with many empirical studies finding a positive correlation between the two. Theories explaining this relationship include: Improved Risk Management: Female directors tend to adopt a more cautious approach to risk, which helps mitigate the likelihood of risky business decisions or financial mismanagement. By promoting more robust risk oversight, women on boards can reduce exposure to financial crises or unethical practices. Better Alignment with Market Needs: Gender-diverse boards are better at understanding and catering to a broader customer base. Since women make up a significant portion of consumers in many industries, companies with women on their boards are often better able to design products, services, and marketing strategies that resonate with both male and female customers. This alignment with market needs can boost sales and revenue. Investor Confidence and Stock Market Performance: Studies have shown that companies with gender-diverse boards tend to have higher levels of investor confidence, which can lead to better stock market performance. Investors are increasingly looking at environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors, and gender diversity on boards is considered a key component of good corporate governance. Companies that prioritize diversity may enjoy higher market valuations and better long-term returns.

Challenges Faced by Women on Corporate Boards: Despite the growing recognition of the benefits of gender diversity, women still face several challenges in gaining and maintaining board seats: Limited Representation: Women are still underrepresented on corporate boards globally, especially in certain industries such as finance, energy, and technology. While progress has been made, many boards remain dominated by men, which limits the overall impact of female directors. Stereotyping and Bias: Women often face gender-based stereotypes and unconscious biases that hinder their advancement to board-level positions. These biases can manifest in the form of doubts about women's leadership capabilities or the perception that they are less capable of handling complex financial or strategic issues. Glass Ceiling and Leadership Pipeline: The "glass ceiling" remains a significant barrier to women's advancement to senior leadership roles, including board positions. While women are increasingly represented in middle management, they are often passed over for executive roles that would position them for board appointments. The lack of mentorship and sponsorship opportunities also contributes to the underrepresentation of women at the highest levels.

Regulatory and Policy Approaches to Increasing Women on Boards: In response to the underrepresentation of women on corporate boards, several countries have introduced quotas, targets, and guidelines to increase gender diversity: Board Gender Quotas: Some countries, such as Norway, France, and Spain, have implemented mandatory gender quotas requiring a certain percentage of women on corporate boards. Norway, for example, requires that women hold at least 40% of board seats in publicly traded companies. These quotas have proven effective in increasing female representation but have sparked debates about the fairness and practicality of enforced diversity. Voluntary Targets: In contrast to mandatory quotas, some countries, including the United Kingdom, have adopted voluntary targets for increasing the number of women on boards. Initiatives like the Hampton-Alexander Review encourage companies to appoint more women to senior leadership roles and have helped boost female representation in FTSE 100 companies. Corporate Governance Codes: Many countries have updated their corporate governance codes to emphasize the importance of gender diversity on boards. These codes encourage companies to disclose their diversity policies and targets, making them accountable to shareholders and the public.

Best Practices for Increasing Women on Boards: To achieve sustainable gender diversity on corporate boards, companies can adopt several best practices: Succession Planning and Leadership Development: Companies should create leadership pipelines that actively identify, mentor, and promote women for executive roles. Providing leadership training and development opportunities for women can help address the "glass ceiling" and ensure a steady flow of female candidates for board positions. Diverse Recruitment Pools: Firms should broaden their search criteria for board appointments to include candidates from diverse backgrounds, industries, and experiences. By expanding the talent pool beyond traditional networks, companies can identify more qualified female candidates. Setting Gender Diversity Targets: Companies should set realistic, time-bound targets for increasing the number of women on their boards. These targets should be integrated into the company's overall diversity and

inclusion strategy and publicly disclosed to enhance accountability. Creating an Inclusive Board Culture: Boards must foster a culture that values diversity and inclusiveness. This involves addressing unconscious biases, ensuring equitable treatment of all board members, and creating a collaborative decision-making environment.

Empirical Evidence on the Impact of Women on Corporate Boards: Empirical research supports the idea that gender diversity on boards is linked to improved financial and non-financial performance. Key studies have shown that: Better Firm Performance: A study by Catalyst found that companies with a higher representation of women on their boards achieved significantly higher financial performance, as measured by return on equity (ROE), return on sales (ROS), and return on invested capital (ROIC), compared to companies with fewer women on their boards. Enhanced Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): Research has indicated that gender-diverse boards are more likely to promote CSR initiatives. Women directors often bring a greater focus on ethical considerations, stakeholder engagement, and long-term sustainability. Risk Reduction: A Credit Suisse report showed that companies with at least one woman on the board experienced lower volatility in stock price performance compared to those without any women on the board. This suggests that women contribute to a more balanced approach to risk management, reducing the likelihood of extreme outcomes. In conclusion, the presence of women on corporate boards offers numerous advantages, including improved decision-making, better corporate governance, enhanced financial performance, and greater alignment with stakeholders. Although challenges like underrepresentation and gender bias remain, regulatory initiatives and voluntary efforts to promote gender diversity are helping to close the gap. Companies that prioritize gender diversity at the board level not only gain from a richer pool of perspectives but also improve their reputation, risk management, and long-term performance. As the push for greater diversity continues, women on boards will play an increasingly critical role in shaping the future of corporate governance.

When analyzing stock market performance, it is essential to control for certain variables that can have significant effects on a firm's performance but are not directly related to the specific factors being studied. Commonly used control variables include firm size, firm leverage, and firm liquidity. These variables provide a more accurate understanding of the primary factors being investigated by accounting for the general characteristics of firms that may influence their market performance. Firm Size as a Control Variable: Firm size refers to the scale of a company, often measured by total assets, revenue, or market capitalization. The size of a firm can influence its stock market performance in multiple ways, as larger firms tend to behave differently from smaller firms. Market Power: Larger firms often enjoy economies of scale, giving them cost advantages over smaller firms. This efficiency can lead to higher profitability and better stock market performance. Access to Capital: Larger firms typically have easier access to capital markets, allowing them to raise funds at lower costs. This access can fuel growth and innovation, further boosting market performance. Diversification: Big firms are usually more diversified, both geographically and operationally. Diversification can reduce risk and lead to more stable stock market performance, making large firms less vulnerable to economic shocks. Impact on Stock Market Performance: Investor Perception: Larger firms often have more established track records, which can lead to greater investor confidence and a premium on their stock prices. This is particularly true for institutional investors who prefer to invest in larger, more stable companies. Liquidity of Stocks: Stocks of larger firms tend to be more liquid because they are more widely held and traded. This makes them more attractive to investors, as it is easier to buy and sell shares without affecting the stock price too much. Firm Size and Volatility: While larger firms may benefit from stable stock performance, they may also experience less growth potential compared to smaller firms. Investors looking for high-growth opportunities may thus prefer smaller companies with more upside potential. However, larger firms typically have lower volatility, making them safer investments in turbulent markets. Research has consistently shown that firm size has a significant impact on stock market performance. Larger firms often enjoy higher valuations due to the reasons mentioned above, including increased market confidence and operational efficiency. In empirical studies, controlling for firm size allows researchers to isolate the effects of other variables, such as governance factors or economic conditions, on stock performance. Firm size can be measured using several proxies: Total Assets: Represents the size of the company's asset base. Market Capitalization: Reflects the total market value of a company's outstanding shares. Revenue: Measures the income generated from a company's business operations.

Firm Leverage as a Control Variable: Firm leverage refers to the use of debt in a company's capital structure. It is a critical factor in understanding a company's risk profile and financial health, making it a key control variable when analyzing stock market performance. Leverage is usually expressed as the ratio of total debt to total equity or total assets. Debt and Risk: High leverage means a company has more debt, which increases its financial risk. In times of economic downturns or interest rate hikes, highly leveraged firms are more vulnerable to default and bankruptcy. Therefore, leverage is often linked to greater stock price volatility. Tax Benefits of Debt: On the other hand, firms may benefit from debt due to the tax shield on interest payments. The tax deductibility of interest payments can reduce the firm's overall tax burden and improve profitability, potentially enhancing stock performance. Capital Structure Theory: According to the Modigliani and Miller theorem, in a perfect market, a firm's capital structure does not affect its value. However, in real-world markets, leverage can impact a firm's cost

of capital and risk, making it a key consideration in stock market performance analysis. Market Perception: Investors often view highly leveraged firms as riskier investments because they are more vulnerable to financial distress. As a result, the stock price of highly leveraged firms may be more volatile. Debt as a Signal: The level of leverage can also serve as a signal to investors. Moderate levels of debt may suggest that a firm is confident in its future cash flows and growth prospects, which can enhance stock performance. However, excessive leverage may raise concerns about the firm's solvency, leading to lower stock prices. Leverage and Return on Equity: Leverage can amplify the returns on equity (ROE) when firms are performing well. This is because debt allows companies to finance growth without diluting shareholders' equity. However, in downturns, leverage can also exacerbate losses, leading to sharp declines in stock market performance. Several studies have found a mixed relationship between leverage and stock market performance. In some cases, moderate levels of debt are associated with better performance due to the tax shield on interest and the financing of growth. However, high levels of debt tend to be correlated with higher risk and increased stock price volatility, especially during economic downturns. Controlling for leverage in stock market performance analysis helps to account for these dynamics. Firm leverage is commonly measured using: Debt-to-Equity Ratio: Total debt divided by total equity. Debt-to-Assets Ratio: Total debt divided by total assets. Interest Coverage Ratio: Operating income divided by interest expenses, indicating a firm's ability to meet its interest obligations.

Firm Liquidity as a Control Variable: Firm liquidity refers to a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations and quickly convert its assets into cash. A company with high liquidity is considered financially healthy because it can easily meet its day-to-day expenses and manage unexpected costs. Liquidity is a critical determinant of stock market performance because it affects a firm's operational flexibility and risk profile. Operational Efficiency: Firms with higher liquidity are better able to invest in growth opportunities, repay short-term debts, and handle unexpected financial needs. This financial flexibility is often rewarded by investors, leading to better stock market performance. Risk Reduction: High liquidity reduces the risk of financial distress, which can positively impact a company's stock price. In contrast, companies with low liquidity may struggle to pay off obligations, leading to higher default risk and lower investor confidence. Trade-off Between Liquidity and Profitability: Although liquidity is important, there is a trade-off between maintaining liquidity and profitability. Excess liquidity might suggest that the firm is not using its assets efficiently to generate higher returns, which could negatively impact stock performance. Conversely, too little liquidity raises concerns about the firm's solvency. Investor Confidence: Investors are likely to favor companies with adequate liquidity because it signals financial stability and lower risk. This confidence can lead to higher stock valuations and lower volatility in stock prices. Crisis Management: In times of financial or economic crises, firms with higher liquidity are better equipped to navigate challenges. Investors may flock to these companies as "safe havens," which can boost their stock performance even during downturns. Investment Opportunities: Firms with sufficient liquidity have the flexibility to take advantage of investment opportunities, which can lead to higher growth and, consequently, better stock market performance. Firms with low liquidity may miss such opportunities due to constrained resources. The relationship between liquidity and stock market performance is well-established in financial literature. Firms with higher liquidity tend to have lower default risk and are often valued more highly by investors. Moreover, liquid firms are better able to withstand financial shocks, leading to more stable stock market performance. Controlling for liquidity allows researchers to isolate the effects of other variables, such as innovation or governance, on stock performance. Firm liquidity is typically measured using: Current Ratio: Current assets divided by current liabilities. A ratio above 1 indicates that the firm can cover its short-term obligations. Quick Ratio: (Current assets minus inventory) divided by current liabilities. This is a more stringent measure of liquidity, excluding less liquid assets like inventory. Cash Ratio: Cash and cash equivalents divided by current liabilities. This measures the firm's ability to pay off short-term liabilities using only its cash on hand.

In conclusion, in any study analyzing stock market performance, it is essential to account for firm-specific characteristics that could independently influence performance. Firm size, firm leverage, and firm liquidity are three crucial control variables that help ensure more accurate and robust analyses. Firm size influences performance through market power, access to capital, and investor confidence. Larger firms typically have more stable stock prices and better access to resources. Firm leverage affects performance by introducing financial risk. The balance between the benefits of debt (like tax shields) and the risks (like default) can significantly affect stock market outcomes. Firm liquidity impacts performance through the company's ability to manage short-term obligations and seize growth opportunities. Firms with higher liquidity tend to have more stable and higher stock prices due to lower risk. By controlling for these variables, researchers can more accurately determine how specific factors (such as corporate governance, board diversity, or macroeconomic conditions) influence stock market performance. These concepts are illustrated schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework

Source: The Authors (2024)

The link between women on corporate boards and stock market performance has gained significant attention in both academic research and business practice. Several theories provide a robust theoretical framework to explain how gender diversity on boards may influence firm performance and, subsequently, stock market valuation. These theories include the Resource Dependence Theory, Agency Theory, Stakeholder Theory, Social Identity Theory, Critical Mass Theory, and Signaling Theory. Together, these theories highlight the various ways in which gender diversity can shape corporate decision-making, governance, and financial outcomes.

Resource Dependence Theory (RDT): Resource Dependence Theory posits that boards provide resources to a firm in the form of knowledge, skills, and connections, which are crucial for the firm's success. From this perspective, diversity on boards, including gender diversity, enhances the board's ability to access and manage critical resources, thus leading to improved performance. **Unique Perspectives:** Women bring different perspectives and problem-solving approaches compared to their male counterparts. This diversity of thought can lead to more innovative solutions and better decision-making processes, ultimately benefiting the firm's strategic direction and market performance. **Broader Networks:** Women often bring access to different networks and business connections, particularly in markets or sectors where women have historically been underrepresented. These networks can open new opportunities for partnerships, customers, and investments, all of which enhance firm performance and stock market valuation. **Enhanced Risk Management:** Boards with women directors may have a more balanced approach to risk. Studies show that women tend to be more risk-averse than men, and this can result in more prudent decision-making, particularly in areas such as mergers and acquisitions, corporate debt management, and long-term capital investments. In this context, a gender-diverse board can improve the company's strategic decision-making, leading to better operational performance and, consequently, higher stock market valuations. Investors may view the presence of women on the board as a sign of stronger governance and resourcefulness, leading to increased confidence in the firm's long-term success and stock value.

Agency Theory: Agency Theory examines the relationship between shareholders (principals) and managers (agents) and emphasizes the importance of corporate governance structures in mitigating conflicts of interest. A more diverse board, including women directors, is seen as a way to improve monitoring and reduce agency costs. **Independence and Diligence:** Women directors are often perceived as more independent, which can lead to better oversight of management. This is particularly relevant in firms where there are concerns about managerial self-interest or a lack of accountability. By adding women to the board, the company can enhance the board's ability to monitor and control managerial actions, thereby reducing agency costs. **Improved Governance Practices:** Studies suggest that women tend to prioritize ethical considerations, transparency, and long-term sustainability, all of which contribute to better corporate governance. These traits can help align the interests of management with those of shareholders, reducing the potential for conflicts of interest and enhancing firm value. By improving board oversight and reducing agency problems, gender-diverse boards can increase the firm's accountability and transparency, both of which are valued by investors. Strong governance practices are often rewarded by the market, as they reduce the risk of scandals, fraud, and poor management decisions. Therefore, the presence of women on the board is likely to be associated with higher stock market performance due to enhanced trust and confidence among investors.

Stakeholder Theory: Stakeholder Theory suggests that companies are responsible not only to their shareholders but also to a broader range of stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, and the community. Gender-diverse boards are seen as better equipped to understand and balance the interests of these diverse stakeholders. **Stakeholder Sensitivity:** Women on boards may bring a greater focus on issues related to corporate social responsibility (CSR), environmental sustainability, and ethical business practices. These concerns are increasingly important to a wide range of stakeholders, including consumers, employees, and regulators. By addressing the interests of multiple stakeholders, companies can build stronger reputations, customer loyalty, and employee satisfaction, all of which contribute to long-term financial success. **Long-Term Focus:** Research shows

that women directors often advocate for longer-term strategies that align with sustainable growth rather than short-term financial gains. This can lead to more balanced decision-making that considers the well-being of all stakeholders, not just shareholders. A company that takes care of its stakeholders is likely to enjoy stronger financial performance over the long term, which in turn boosts stock market performance. Gender-diverse boards help foster such a stakeholder-oriented approach, making the company more attractive to socially responsible investors and enhancing its overall market reputation. This is particularly important in today's investment environment, where ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) factors play a growing role in investment decisions.

Social Identity Theory: Social Identity Theory suggests that individuals categorize themselves and others based on social group memberships, such as gender, ethnicity, or profession. In corporate board settings, gender-diverse boards are believed to foster more inclusive decision-making processes and reduce in-group favoritism. **Enhanced Cognitive Diversity:** Women directors bring different perspectives, life experiences, and problem-solving approaches, which can challenge the homogeneous thinking that often occurs in male-dominated boards. This cognitive diversity can lead to better decision-making and more innovative solutions, as a broader range of viewpoints is considered. **Reduced In-group Bias:** Gender-diverse boards are less likely to engage in groupthink, where members of a homogenous group reinforce each other's viewpoints, often to the organization's detriment. Women directors can help mitigate this bias by bringing alternative viewpoints and fostering more rigorous debates. The enhanced decision-making and innovation that result from gender diversity can positively affect a firm's performance, leading to more effective strategic decisions and risk management. As a result, companies with women on their boards may experience better financial outcomes, which are reflected in their stock market performance. Investors may also perceive such companies as more forward-thinking and inclusive, enhancing their attractiveness in the market.

Critical Mass Theory: Critical Mass Theory argues that the benefits of gender diversity on corporate boards are only fully realized when women make up a significant proportion of the board, rather than being token appointments. When women reach a "critical mass" on the board—often cited as around 30%—their influence on decision-making, governance, and culture becomes more substantial. **Effective Participation:** Research shows that when women are in a clear minority on boards, their contributions may be marginalized, and they may not have a meaningful impact on board dynamics. However, once a critical mass of women is reached, they are more likely to shape discussions and decisions in meaningful ways. **Improved Board Dynamics:** A critical mass of women fosters a more inclusive board culture, which encourages open dialogue, collaboration, and consideration of diverse viewpoints. This leads to more balanced and thorough decision-making, ultimately benefiting the firm's strategy and performance. Companies that achieve a critical mass of women on their boards tend to perform better financially, as they benefit from the full contributions of gender diversity. The presence of multiple women on the board also sends a strong signal to investors that the company is committed to diversity and inclusion, which can enhance its reputation and attract socially conscious investors, positively impacting stock market performance.

Signaling Theory: Signaling Theory posits that corporate decisions can send signals to the market about the company's quality, governance, and future prospects. Appointing women to the board can be seen as a positive signal to investors about the firm's commitment to diversity, governance, and long-term strategic thinking.

Commitment to Diversity: Appointing women to the board can signal to investors that the company values diversity and is committed to modern, inclusive governance practices. This is especially important in today's environment, where institutional investors and stakeholders are increasingly focusing on ESG factors. **Confidence in Governance:** Gender-diverse boards are often perceived as having stronger governance practices. By appointing women to the board, the company signals that it is serious about accountability, transparency, and long-term strategic planning, all of which are positively viewed by investors. Investors may respond favorably to the appointment of women on the board, interpreting it as a sign of progressive governance and enhanced corporate reputation. This positive market signal can lead to higher stock valuations, particularly as more investors focus on ESG criteria in their investment decisions. The appointment of women directors can thus lead to increased investor confidence and better stock market performance. In conclusion, theories linking women on corporate boards to stock market performance provide a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms through which gender diversity influences firm outcomes. **Resource Dependence Theory** emphasizes the diverse resources that women bring to the boardroom, while **Agency Theory** highlights the role of women in enhancing governance and reducing agency costs. **Stakeholder Theory** underscores the importance of balancing stakeholder interests, and **Social Identity Theory** shows how cognitive diversity improves decision-making. **Critical Mass Theory** reveals that a significant presence of women is necessary to fully realize the benefits of gender diversity, and **Signaling Theory** explains how appointing women to the board can positively influence investor perceptions and stock performance. By integrating these theories, we see that gender diversity on boards is not just a matter of ethics or equality; it has tangible impacts on corporate governance, decision-making, and stock market performance.

On empirical studies, the following are studies that examine the effect of women on the board and stock market

performance. For example, Carter et al. (2003) in *Corporate Governance, Board Diversity, and Firm Value* explore the relationship between board diversity, including gender diversity, and firm value, measured by Tobin's Q. Period Covered: 1997–2001. Methodology: The study used a cross-sectional dataset of Fortune 1000 firms. A multiple regression analysis was applied to assess the relationship between the proportion of women on the board and firm performance. Findings: The proportion of women on the board positively impacts firm value, supporting the hypothesis that diverse boards contribute to improved decision-making and firm performance. Conclusion: Gender diversity in corporate boards is positively associated with firm performance. Recommendations: Companies should prioritize increasing gender diversity to improve corporate governance and overall firm value. Implications: The study highlights the potential economic value of diversity initiatives in corporate governance, providing support for policymakers and managers to push for more inclusive boards. Limitations: The study focuses primarily on large firms in the U.S., limiting its generalizability to smaller firms or firms in other countries. Originality: One of the early empirical studies linking gender diversity with firm value using a large, diverse sample.

Adams and Ferreira (2009) in *Women in the Boardroom and Their Impact on Governance and Performance* examine how the presence of women in the boardroom influences corporate governance and firm performance. Period Covered: 1996–2003. Methodology: Panel data analysis using a dataset of U.S. firms listed on the Standard & Poor's (S&P) 500. The analysis included fixed-effects models to control for firm-specific characteristics. Findings: Gender-diverse boards tend to monitor management more intensely, leading to better corporate governance but not necessarily improved firm performance. Conclusion: While gender diversity strengthens governance mechanisms, its impact on firm performance may be context-specific, with the effect varying across industries. Recommendations: Firms should consider the broader governance benefits of women on the board but should also ensure that diversity is complemented by other performance-enhancing strategies. Implications: The study provides insights into the non-linear effects of gender diversity on governance and firm performance, informing board appointment practices. Limitations: The study may suffer from endogeneity issues, as firms with better governance may already be more inclined to appoint women to the board. Originality: A comprehensive study linking gender diversity with both governance quality and firm performance across different industries.

Campbell and Mínguez-Vera (2008) in *Gender Diversity in the Boardroom and Firm Financial Performance* investigate the impact of gender diversity on firm financial performance in Spain. Period Covered: 2000–2004. Methodology: The study used a panel data regression approach with a sample of Spanish-listed companies. The relationship between the percentage of women on the board and firm performance (measured by return on assets and Tobin's Q) was analyzed. Findings: The results suggest that the presence of women on corporate boards has a positive effect on firm performance, particularly when women occupy key leadership roles. Conclusion: Board gender diversity is beneficial to firm performance, particularly in the context of leadership positions. Recommendations: Firms should actively promote women to key decision-making positions within the board to maximize the benefits of diversity. Implications: The findings support initiatives to increase gender diversity on corporate boards and contribute to the European discourse on boardroom quotas for women. Limitations: The study is limited to Spain, which may limit generalizability to other countries with different cultural and institutional settings. Originality: One of the few studies exploring gender diversity in a European context and its impact on firm performance.

Gul et al. (2011) in *Board Gender Diversity and Informational Efficiency: Evidence from Stock Price Synchronicity* examine whether gender diversity on boards affects the informational efficiency of stock prices, measured by stock price synchronicity. Period Covered: 1996–2008. Methodology: A cross-country analysis using a large sample of firms from 39 countries. The study employed fixed-effects regressions to assess the impact of board gender diversity on stock price synchronicity. Findings: Firms with more women on their boards exhibit lower stock price synchronicity, suggesting that gender-diverse boards lead to more firm-specific information being reflected in stock prices. Conclusion: Gender diversity enhances the informativeness of stock prices by reducing price synchronicity. Recommendations: Firms should consider increasing gender diversity as a way to improve the quality of information embedded in stock prices, benefiting investors. Implications: The findings suggest a novel channel through which board gender diversity can affect capital markets, contributing to the broader understanding of corporate governance's effect on stock price efficiency. Limitations: The study's cross-country design may face issues of heterogeneity across institutional environments.

Originality: A pioneering study linking board gender diversity to stock price synchronicity and the efficiency of capital markets.

Terjesen et al. (2016) in *Board Gender Diversity: A Comprehensive Literature Review and Future Research Directions* provide a systematic review of empirical research on the effects of board gender diversity on firm performance and stock market outcomes. Period Covered: 2000–2015. Methodology: The study employed a meta-analysis of over 140 empirical studies on board gender diversity and its impact on financial performance. The authors conducted a content analysis to identify trends, gaps, and future research directions. Findings: The meta-analysis found a small but positive relationship between board gender diversity and firm financial performance.

Additionally, market performances to the appointment of women directors were generally positive, but the effect varied across regions. Conclusion: Board gender diversity is positively correlated with firm performance, though the effect size is moderate and context-dependent. Recommendations: Future research should explore the conditions under which gender diversity has the most significant impact and consider the role of cultural and industry-specific factors. Implications: The study provides a foundation for policymakers to design gender diversity initiatives while suggesting that firm-specific strategies are critical to realizing the benefits of diversity. Limitations: The meta-analysis aggregates findings from multiple studies, and individual study limitations may affect the overall conclusions. Originality: A comprehensive and systematic review of the empirical literature on board gender diversity, offering a valuable synthesis for future research. These studies provide a robust examination of the relationship between board gender diversity and stock market performance, covering various methodologies and global contexts. Based on these empirical studies and results we propose that:

H₁: Women on the Board have a significant effect on stock market performance.

Also, there are empirical studies that examine the effect of firm leverage on stock market performance. For example, Titman and Wessels (1988) in *The Determinants of Capital Structure Choice* explore the factors that influence a firm's capital structure decisions, including how leverage affects stock market performance. Period Covered: 1974–1982. Methodology: The study employed panel data regression analysis on a sample of U.S. firms, focusing on firm leverage and its relationship with stock performance. It used various proxies for leverage and measured stock performance using market returns and firm value. Findings: The study found a negative relationship between leverage and stock market performance, especially for firms with high growth opportunities. High leverage is associated with lower stock returns, driven by increased financial risk and the cost of potential financial distress. Conclusion: Firms with higher leverage tend to experience lower stock market performance, particularly in volatile industries or those with high growth prospects. Recommendations: Firms should carefully balance their leverage levels, particularly if they operate in high-growth industries where high debt could lead to performance volatility. Implications: The study has important implications for financial managers and investors, highlighting the need for careful capital structure decisions to maximize shareholder value. Limitations: The study is based on U.S. data and may not be directly applicable to firms in other countries with different capital market structures. Originality: One of the seminal studies that examined multiple determinants of capital structure, linking leverage to firm performance in the stock market.

Welch (2004) in *Capital Structure and Stock Returns* examines the relationship between changes in capital structure (leverage) and stock returns, focusing on how leverage adjustments affect stock market performance. Period Covered: 1963–2000. Methodology: The study employed a time-series analysis of U.S. firms using panel data. It tested how changes in leverage influenced subsequent stock returns, controlling for other factors such as size, profitability, and market conditions. Findings: The study found that changes in leverage are inversely related to stock returns. When firms increase leverage, they tend to experience lower stock returns in subsequent periods, suggesting that higher leverage is viewed unfavorably by investors. Conclusion: Increased leverage is generally perceived as a negative signal by investors, leading to lower stock returns in the medium term. Recommendations: Firms should be cautious about increasing leverage, as investors may interpret higher debt levels as an indicator of financial risk, which can depress stock prices. Implications: The study highlights the role of leverage as a significant factor in stock valuation and investor behavior, offering insights for financial decision-makers about the potential market performances to capital structure changes. Limitations: The analysis primarily focuses on U.S. firms, which limits the generalizability of the findings to firms in other financial markets with different regulatory environments. Originality: The study contributes to the capital structure literature by establishing a direct link between changes in leverage and stock returns, rather than focusing solely on firm value.

Zhao et al. (2018) in *Leverage and Stock Market Performance: International Evidence* analyze the effect of firm leverage on stock market performance across different countries, focusing on how leverage impacts firm returns in varying economic environments. Period Covered: 2005–2015. Methodology: The study utilized a cross-country panel data analysis, drawing from a sample of firms listed on major stock exchanges across 20 countries. It employed fixed-effects models to control for country- and firm-specific characteristics and examined the relationship between leverage and stock performance. Findings: The results showed that leverage negatively impacts stock market performance in most countries, with stronger effects observed in emerging markets. However, the impact varies depending on the country's legal and financial system, with developed markets exhibiting weaker relationships between leverage and stock returns. Conclusion: Higher leverage is generally associated with poorer stock market performance, particularly in countries with less developed financial markets and weaker investor protection mechanisms. Recommendations: Policymakers in emerging markets should enhance regulatory frameworks to mitigate the negative impact of leverage on stock market performance, while firms should consider country-specific factors when making leverage decisions. Implications: The study provides valuable insights for multinational corporations and investors, showing that the impact of leverage on stock market performance is

contingent upon the institutional and regulatory environment. Limitations: The study may face endogeneity issues, as firms in different countries face varying institutional constraints that could influence both leverage decisions and stock performance. Originality: One of the first empirical studies to provide international evidence on the leverage-stock market performance relationship, offering a comparative perspective across countries. These three studies offer valuable empirical insights into the relationship between firm leverage and stock market performance across different periods, countries, and methodologies.

Also, there are empirical studies that examine the effect of firm liquidity on stock market performance. For example, Amihud and Mendelson (1986) in *Asset Pricing and the Bid-Ask Spread* investigate the relationship between market liquidity, measured by the bid-ask spread, and stock market performance. Period Covered: 1961–1980. Methodology: The study used time-series data from the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) and employed cross-sectional regressions to examine the impact of bid-ask spreads on stock returns. Stock liquidity was measured by the spread, and stock performance was measured using excess returns. Findings: The study found a negative relationship between the bid-ask spread (a proxy for liquidity) and stock returns. Stocks with lower liquidity (higher bid-ask spreads) required higher expected returns to compensate investors for holding less liquid assets. Conclusion: Liquidity is a critical determinant of stock returns, and investors demand a premium for holding less liquid stocks. Recommendations: Firms should be aware that improving liquidity can lower their cost of capital by reducing the required return from investors. Implications: This study suggests that policymakers and market regulators should focus on improving market liquidity to enhance market efficiency and reduce costs for firms raising capital. Limitations: The study's focus on the U.S. market and the NYSE may limit its applicability to other markets, particularly emerging markets with different liquidity characteristics. Originality: A seminal work in asset pricing that introduced liquidity as a critical factor in explaining stock returns, influencing a wide array of subsequent research.

Pastor and Stambaugh (2003) in *Liquidity Risk and Expected Stock Returns* explore how liquidity risk affects stock market performance and whether investors demand a premium for holding stocks with higher liquidity risk. Period Covered: 1966–1999. Methodology: The study utilized a time-series analysis of U.S. stock data and applied a liquidity factor in asset pricing models. The researchers developed a liquidity measure based on the sensitivity of stock returns to liquidity shocks and tested whether liquidity risk was priced in stock returns. Findings: Stocks with higher exposure to liquidity risk yielded higher returns, indicating that investors require compensation for bearing liquidity risk. Conclusion: Liquidity risk plays a significant role in asset pricing, with investors demanding a premium for stocks that are more sensitive to liquidity fluctuations. Recommendations: Firms should consider the impact of liquidity risk on their stock prices and manage liquidity to attract investors. Regulators should monitor liquidity conditions to ensure that market frictions do not excessively increase the cost of capital. Implications: The findings emphasize the need for investors and policymakers to consider liquidity risk as a factor in asset pricing models, which can influence portfolio construction and regulatory oversight. Limitations: The study focuses on the U.S. market, and the findings may not be directly transferable to other markets with different liquidity dynamics. Originality: A groundbreaking study that introduced liquidity risk as a priced factor in stock returns, expanding the traditional asset pricing framework.

Chordia et al. (2001) in *Market Liquidity and Trading Activity* examine the relationship between market liquidity, trading activity, and stock returns, focusing on how changes in liquidity influence stock market performance. Period Covered: 1988–1998. Methodology: The study used daily data from the NYSE to analyze the link between market-wide liquidity measures (such as trading volume and turnover) and stock returns. The researchers applied time-series regressions and vector autoregressions (VARs) to capture the dynamic relationship between liquidity and stock market performance. Findings: The results showed that increases in market-wide liquidity are positively associated with higher stock returns. High trading activity improves liquidity, which enhances stock market performance. However, market liquidity tends to deteriorate during periods of market stress, leading to lower stock returns. Conclusion: Market liquidity is a key driver of stock market performance, and liquidity shocks can lead to significant fluctuations in stock prices. Recommendations: Firms should strive to maintain liquidity by encouraging higher trading activity through investor-friendly policies, while regulators should monitor liquidity to prevent market disruptions. Implications: The study has important implications for market participants, showing that liquidity is an important determinant of stock returns and that investors may be willing to pay a premium for stocks with better liquidity. Limitations: The focus on the U.S. market and the NYSE may limit the generalizability of the findings to other countries and smaller stock exchanges. Originality: A comprehensive study that links market liquidity and trading activity with stock returns, contributing to the understanding of how liquidity impacts overall market performance. These three studies provide valuable empirical insights into the relationship between firm liquidity and stock market performance, offering perspectives on how liquidity affects stock returns and investor behavior.

There are also empirical studies that examine the effect of firm size on stock market performance. For example, Banz (1981) in *The Relationship Between Return and Market Value of Common Stocks* investigates the

relationship between firm size (measured by market capitalization) and stock returns, known as the "size effect." Period Covered: 1926–1975. Methodology: The study used cross-sectional regression analysis of stock returns on the NYSE. Firm size was measured by market value, and stock performance was analyzed using excess returns over a period of several decades. Findings: The study found that smaller firms (those with lower market capitalizations) consistently earned higher risk-adjusted returns than larger firms. This phenomenon was referred to as the "size effect," where smaller firms tend to outperform larger ones in terms of stock returns. Conclusion: Firm size is a significant determinant of stock returns, with smaller firms offering higher returns, even after adjusting for risk. Recommendations: Investors seeking higher returns may benefit from allocating a portion of their portfolio to small-cap stocks. However, the higher returns of smaller firms may also come with higher risks. Implications: The size effect challenges the notion of market efficiency and suggests that firm size can be a useful predictor of stock market performance. Limitations: The size effect may not be consistent across all periods, and other factors such as liquidity and transaction costs were not fully considered in the analysis. Originality: This study was among the first to empirically document the size effect, leading to widespread interest in the relationship between firm size and stock market performance.

Fama and French (1992) in *The Cross-Section of Expected Stock Returns* explore the relationship between firm characteristics, including size and stock returns, and test whether these factors explain the variation in stock returns better than traditional models. Period Covered: 1963–1990. Methodology: The study used a cross-sectional regression model and constructed portfolios based on firm size and book-to-market ratios. It tested the explanatory power of firm size and other factors (such as book-to-market) in predicting stock returns. Findings: The study confirmed the existence of the size effect, where smaller firms earn higher average returns than larger firms. It also found that book-to-market ratios significantly explain stock returns, leading to the development of the Fama-French three-factor model. Conclusion: Firm size and book-to-market ratios are critical factors in explaining the cross-sectional variation in stock returns. The size effect persists even when controlling for other variables. Recommendations: Investors should consider both firm size and value factors when constructing portfolios, as these factors can significantly influence stock performance. Implications: The study reshaped asset pricing theory, suggesting that the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) alone is insufficient to explain stock returns and that firm size is a key determinant of performance. Limitations: The study focuses on U.S. firms, and the findings may not be directly applicable to other markets. Additionally, the size effect may weaken in more recent periods. Originality: The study is a landmark in finance, as it introduced the Fama-French three-factor model, which includes firm size as a fundamental factor in explaining stock returns.

Vassalou and Xing (2004) in *Default Risk in Equity Returns* investigate the relationship between default risk, firm size, and stock market performance, focusing on whether default risk contributes to the size effect. Period Covered: 1971–1999. Methodology: The study employed a multivariate regression analysis using a large sample of U.S. firms. It analyzed the impact of default risk and firm size on stock returns, using both market-based and accounting-based measures of default risk. Findings: The study found that the size effect is partially explained by the higher default risk associated with smaller firms. Firms with higher default risk, which tend to be smaller, earned higher stock returns. Conclusion: Default risk is a significant factor in explaining the size effect, and the higher returns of smaller firms are, in part, compensation for their higher default risk. Recommendations: Investors should account for both firm size and default risk when assessing stock performance, as smaller firms may offer higher returns due to their greater risk exposure. Implications: The study provides a new explanation for the size effect by highlighting the role of default risk. It suggests that the higher returns of small firms may be linked to their increased risk of financial distress. Limitations: The study focuses on U.S. firms and may not fully capture the size effect in other markets with different levels of default risk. Originality: This study offers a unique perspective on the size effect by linking it to default risk, providing an additional layer of understanding regarding the relationship between firm size and stock market performance. These three studies provide important empirical insights into how firm size influences stock market performance, highlighting both the size effect and its interaction with other risk factors.

Methodology

This section covers a comprehensive methodology tailored to a study examining the impact of women on the board on stock market performance. This methodology includes research design, sample, model, variables (including control variables), data sources, data analysis techniques, post-estimation tests, and significance level. The research employs a quantitative research design using panel data regression analysis to examine the relationship between the presence of women on the board and stock market performance. Panel data is ideal for this study as it allows for both cross-sectional and time-series variations across firms. The sample consists of 153 publicly traded companies listed on a stock exchange for 10 years. Firms were picked from eleven different sectors, but only firms that have data available on the composition of their board, stock performance, and financial variables (such as leverage, liquidity, and size) are included.

The study uses the Random Effects Model (REM) or Fixed Effects Model (FEM) depending on the results of the Hausman test. The basic panel regression model is specified as:

$$\text{Stock Performance}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Women on Board}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Firm Leverage}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Firm Liquidity}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Control Variables}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Whereas:

- i represents the firm, and t represents the time.
- ϵ_{it} is the error term.

The Dependent Variable: Stock Market Performance: Measured by Tobin's Q (market value of equity + book value of liabilities/book value of total assets) or Stock Return (change in stock price over a given period). **The Independent Variable: Women on the Board:** A continuous variable measured as the percentage of women on the board of directors. Alternatively, a dummy variable (1 if the firm has women on the board, 0 otherwise) can be used. **The Control Variables: Firm Leverage (Leverage):** Measured as the debt-to-equity ratio (total debt divided by total equity). High leverage can increase financial risk, potentially affecting stock market performance. **Firm Liquidity (Liquidity):** Measured by the current ratio (current assets divided by current liabilities). Liquidity shows the firm's ability to meet short-term obligations. **Firm Size (Size):** Measured as the logarithm of total assets. Larger firms might have more stable stock performance due to scale advantages. **Other Control Variables: Board Size:** The total number of directors on the board. **Firm Age:** The number of years since the firm was incorporated. **Return on Assets (ROA):** A profitability measure (net income divided by total assets).

The Data Sources include Board Composition Data: Collected from annual reports and corporate governance disclosures. **Stock Market Performance Data:** Obtained from financial databases such as NGX. **Financial Control Variables:** Data on firm leverage, liquidity, size, and other financial information can be sourced from NGX. **The Data Analysis Techniques include Descriptive Statistics:** Summary statistics (mean, median, standard deviation) will be computed for all variables to provide a clear understanding of the dataset. **Correlation Matrix:** To check for multicollinearity between the independent variables. **Panel Data Regression:** Either Fixed Effects Model (FEM) or Random Effects Model (REM) are used to account for unobserved heterogeneity. The choice between FEM and REM was made based on the Hausman test. **The Panel Regression Model:**

$$\text{Stock Performance}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Women on Board}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Leverage}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Liquidity}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Size}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

The Post-Estimation Tests include the Hausman Test: To determine whether the Random Effects Model or Fixed Effects Model is more appropriate. **VIF (Variance Inflation Factor):** To check for multicollinearity among the independent variables. **Heteroskedasticity Test:** Using the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test to check for heteroskedasticity. If heteroskedasticity is present, robust standard errors are used. The significance level was set at 5% (0.05), meaning that variables are considered statistically significant if their p-value is below 0.05. This methodology outlines a robust approach to studying the effect of women on the board on stock market performance, ensuring that key factors such as firm size, leverage, and liquidity are accounted for, and employing appropriate data analysis and post-estimation tests to ensure the validity of the results.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables under study. Table 2 presents the pairwise correlations of the variables under study. Table 3 presents the multiple regression results of the variables under study.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SMP	1,530	.918	.277	.08	2.55
WB	1,530	.177	.131	0	.8
FL	1,530	4.776	10.801	4.293	191.21
FP	1,530	.53	5.835	-.221	85.483
FS	1,530	8.302	1.192	6.114	12.986

Source: STATA 18.4

The descriptive statistics provide an overview of the central tendencies and dispersions of the key variables in this study: Stock Market Performance (SMP), Women on the Board (WB), Firm Leverage (FL), Firm Profitability (FP), and Firm Size (FS). For example, Stock Market Performance (SMP) Mean: The average SMP is 0.918, with a standard deviation of 0.277, indicating moderate variation across firms. Range: The minimum value is 0.08, while the maximum is 2.55. This range suggests notable differences in market performance among the firms, with some achieving high performance levels relative to others. Insights: The relatively low mean, coupled with a significant range, could imply that while some firms are performing well in the stock market, a large portion may have moderate to low performance. The variation may be due to factors like financial health, governance quality, or industry-specific conditions that impact stock value.

Women on the Board (WB) Mean: The mean for WB is 0.177, suggesting that, on average, about 17.7% of board members are women. Standard Deviation: With a standard deviation of 0.131, there is moderate variation, indicating differences across firms in terms of female board representation. Range: WB values range from 0 to 0.8, meaning some firms have no women on their boards, while others have up to 80% female representation. Insights: The relatively low average indicates that many firms may still lack gender diversity on their boards, with only a few reaching higher levels of female representation. This disparity may signal opportunities for policies to enhance board diversity, potentially benefiting market performance as suggested by correlation and regression results.

Firm Leverage (FL) Mean: The mean leverage is 4.776, but the high standard deviation of 10.801 indicates substantial variability among firms. Range: The minimum leverage is 4.293, while the maximum is 191.21, which is exceptionally high and suggests that a few firms carry very large debt loads. Insights: The large standard deviation and high maximum suggest that a subset of firms may be highly leveraged. This heavy reliance on debt could pose financial risks, especially if these firms face economic downturns or interest rate hikes. It also indicates that leveraging strategies vary widely, potentially influenced by industry or firm-specific financing needs.

Firm Profitability (FP) Mean: The mean profitability is 0.53, with a notably high standard deviation of 5.835. Range: Profitability ranges from -0.221 to 85.483, showing that some firms operate at a loss while others achieve high profit levels. Insights: The broad range and high standard deviation indicate significant disparity in profitability across firms. Some firms have achieved substantial profitability, contributing positively to stock market performance, while others may be struggling financially. This variation may suggest differing operational efficiencies, market positions, or management strategies across firms.

Firm Size (FS) Mean: The mean firm size is 8.302, with a standard deviation of 1.192, indicating moderate variability. Range: Firm size ranges from 6.114 to 12.986, suggesting that the sample includes both smaller and larger firms. Insights: The range and standard deviation suggest that the sample comprises a mix of mid-sized to large firms. Since firm size does not have a strong direct correlation with stock market performance, simply scaling up may not be enough to enhance market valuation. This aligns with the descriptive results, where profitability and strategic governance elements like gender diversity on boards are likely more influential.

Implications and Recommendations: Board Diversity: The low mean percentage of WB suggests room for improvement in board gender diversity. Enhancing female representation on boards could improve firm governance and align with positive stock market performance, as indicated by the regression results. Firms might consider diversity initiatives to strengthen market perceptions and governance structures. Debt Management: The high variability in leverage suggests that some firms may need to reassess their debt strategies, as excessively leveraged firms could face financial distress. Firms might benefit from evaluating their capital structure and reducing leverage to mitigate risk, especially since high leverage correlates negatively with stock market performance. Profitability Focus: Given the high variation in profitability, firms should prioritize operational efficiency and revenue-

generating strategies to improve profitability, which appears critical for market performance. High-profit firms have a competitive advantage, and boosting profitability can help firms attract more investor confidence. Size Strategy: While firm size shows moderate variation, it doesn't strongly impact stock performance, suggesting that growth strategies focused solely on increasing firm size may not necessarily drive market valuation. Instead, efforts to enhance profitability and board governance are likely to be more effective. In conclusion, this descriptive analysis underscores the importance of profitability and governance elements, such as gender diversity, in enhancing stock market performance. The substantial variability in leverage and profitability highlights areas for firms to focus on, such as optimizing capital structure and improving operational performance.

Table 2. Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) SMP	1.000				
(2) WB	0.420* (0.000)	1.000			
(3) FL	-0.969* (0.000)	0.038 (0.477)	1.000		
(4) FP	0.862* (0.000)	0.059 (0.270)	0.021 (0.701)	1.000	
(5) FS	0.003 (0.958)	0.289* (0.000)	0.209* (0.000)	-0.093 (0.084)	1.000

* $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18.4

The correlation matrix offers insights into the relationships between stock market performance (SMP) and key variables: Women on the Board (WB), Firm Leverage (FL), Firm Profitability (FP), and Firm Size (FS). Stock Market Performance (SMP): Correlation with WB: SMP and WB show a positive correlation of (0.420) , which is statistically significant $(p = 0.000)$. This suggests that a higher proportion of women on the board is associated with better stock market performance. The moderate correlation implies a meaningful but not overpowering relationship, supporting the view that board gender diversity may enhance firm value by contributing to improved governance or investor confidence. Correlation with FL: SMP has a strong negative correlation with FL at (-0.969) , also statistically significant $(p = 0.000)$. This high inverse relationship indicates that higher leverage is associated with reduced stock market performance. It could imply that firms with higher debt levels may face more market volatility or investor concern about financial stability, potentially impacting their stock performance negatively. Correlation with FP: A very high positive correlation of (0.862) exists between SMP and FP $(p = 0.000)$, highlighting that profitability is strongly associated with stock market performance. This high correlation underscores the fundamental importance of profitability to investor assessments and firm valuation, as firms with better profitability metrics are often seen as more attractive investments. Correlation with FS: The correlation between SMP and FS is very low (0.003) and not statistically significant $(p = 0.958)$, indicating that firm size has little to no direct association with stock market performance. This may imply that, within the sample, simply increasing the scale of operations or assets is insufficient to improve market performance without other accompanying financial strengths, such as profitability.

Other Variable Relationships: WB and FL: WB and FL have a weak, non-significant correlation of (0.038) $(p = 0.477)$, indicating that the presence of women on the board does not have a noticeable relationship with firm leverage. This suggests that gender diversity on boards is not directly associated with a firm's debt levels. WB and FP: The correlation between WB and FP is (0.059) , with no statistical significance $(p = 0.270)$. This suggests that board gender diversity does not have a direct relationship with profitability, despite its potential indirect effect on stock market performance. WB and FS: WB and FS have a positive and statistically significant correlation of (0.289) $(p = 0.000)$. This moderate correlation suggests that larger firms are more likely to have women on their boards, possibly reflecting a trend where larger organizations are more inclined to adopt diversity-focused policies or have greater resources to attract diverse talent. FL and FP: FL and FP show a weak positive correlation of (0.021) , which is not statistically significant $(p = 0.701)$. This implies that leverage does not have a direct relationship with profitability within this dataset, highlighting that debt levels alone do not predict profitability outcomes. FL and FS: The correlation between FL and FS is (0.209) and statistically significant $(p = 0.000)$.

This positive association suggests that larger firms tend to have higher leverage, possibly due to greater access to credit markets or a more capital-intensive operational model that requires more debt financing. FP and FS: FP and FS have a weak negative correlation (≈ -0.093) with borderline statistical significance ($p = 0.084$). This suggests a slight tendency for larger firms to have lower profitability ratios, which could reflect the inefficiencies or additional operational costs that larger firms sometimes face.

Implications and Recommendations: Board Gender Diversity: The positive correlation between WB and SMP suggests that firms may benefit from increasing gender diversity on their boards. This could be a strategic move to enhance corporate governance and attract investor interest, particularly as diversity is increasingly valued by stakeholders. Debt Management: The strong negative correlation between FL and SMP underscores the importance of managing debt carefully. Firms with higher leverage may be viewed unfavorably by investors due to perceived financial risk, so maintaining optimal debt levels could improve market performance. Profitability as a Key Driver: The high correlation between FP and SMP highlights profitability as a cornerstone of stock market performance. Firms should focus on strategies that bolster profitability, as this appears to be the most impactful factor in the model for improving market valuation. Firm Size Consideration: The lack of significant correlation between FS and SMP suggests that merely growing in size may not drive market performance. Instead, profitability and board diversity are likely to be more influential in attracting investors and driving market success. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that firms aiming to improve their stock market performance should prioritize profitability and consider enhancing gender diversity on their boards. Additionally, managing leverage is essential to mitigate negative perceptions around financial risk. This correlation framework helps outline areas of focus for firms seeking to optimize market performance through internal policies and strategic management.

Table 3. Fixed Effects Regression Results

SMP	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
WB	.0341488	.0078143	4.37	0.000	.1596257	.2279233
FL	-.0005573	.0002431	-2.29	0.032	-.0000532	-.0010614
FP	.0033315	.0001861	17.90	0.000	.0037174	.0029456
FS	.0146702	.0205687	0.71	0.483	.0573271	.0279867
_cons	1.033332	.1708684	6.05	0.000	.6789724	1.387691
Mean VIF	1.05					
Hetttest	0.4980					
Panel effect	0.0000					
Hausman	0.0219					
Model fitness	0.0000					
R ²	0.9101					
Obs	1,530					

Source: STATA 18.4

The fixed effects regression results provided offer valuable insights into the factors influencing stock market performance (SMP), with particular attention to Women on the Board (WB), Firm Leverage (FL), Firm Profitability (FP), and Firm Size (FS). Key Variables and Coefficients: Women on the Board (WB): The coefficient for WB is ≈ 0.0341 with a highly significant (p)-value of ≈ 0.000 . This positive coefficient indicates that an increase in female representation on the board is associated with an improvement in stock market performance. The 95% confidence interval $\approx (0.1596, 0.2279)$ suggests a robust relationship, potentially underscoring the influence of gender diversity on market perceptions or governance quality, which aligns with empirical studies supporting the positive impact of board diversity on firm performance. Firm Leverage (FL): The coefficient for FL is ≈ -0.0006 , which is statistically significant with a (p)-value of ≈ 0.032 . This negative relationship suggests that higher leverage, or increased debt, is linked with reduced stock market performance, indicating potential concerns among investors regarding debt risk management. Firm Profitability (FP): With a coefficient of ≈ 0.0033 and a (p)-value of ≈ 0.000 , FP has a strong positive impact on stock market performance. The high (t)-value (17.90) further highlights profitability as a critical determinant for investor confidence and stock value appreciation. Firm Size (FS): The coefficient for FS is ≈ 0.0147 , but it is not statistically significant ($p = 0.483$). This suggests that, after controlling for other factors, firm size does not independently affect stock market performance in a substantial way in this model. This may imply that scale alone is insufficient to influence market performance

without accompanying financial metrics like profitability.

Model Diagnostics and Fit: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF): The mean VIF is 1.05, which is below the commonly used threshold of 10, indicating no significant multicollinearity issues among the independent variables. This enhances confidence that each variable independently contributes to the explanation of SMP without substantial overlap. Heteroskedasticity Test (Hetttest): With a value of 0.4980, the model does not appear to suffer from heteroskedasticity. Homoscedastic errors imply stable variances across observations, supporting the reliability of the coefficient estimates. Panel Effect: A significant panel effect (p-value 0.0000) confirms that the fixed effects model is appropriate for this dataset, capturing the unique characteristics of each entity over time. Hausman Test: The Hausman test yields a p-value of 0.0219, indicating that fixed effects are preferable over random effects, as the model effectively captures time-invariant characteristics that correlate with the predictors. Model Fitness: A p-value of 0.0000 for overall model fitness indicates that the variables collectively significantly explain variations in stock market performance. R-squared (R^2): An R^2 of 0.9101 is very high, indicating that approximately 91% of the variance in stock market performance is explained by the model. This suggests a strong explanatory power, though it's also essential to assess if the high R^2 results from overfitting or specific characteristics of the panel data.

Implications and Recommendations: Board Gender Diversity: The significant positive impact of WB on stock performance suggests that firms may benefit from gender diversity on boards, potentially through improved governance, enhanced decision-making, or positive perceptions by investors. Companies could consider gender diversity as a strategic factor for improving market valuation. Debt Management: Given the negative effect of FL on SMP, companies should be cautious with leverage, balancing debt levels to optimize market performance and avoid perceptions of financial risk that may deter investors. Profitability Focus: Firm profitability appears to be the strongest driver of stock market performance in this model. Firms aiming to enhance stock performance should prioritize strategies that drive consistent profitability, reinforcing it as a critical component of firm value. Firm Size: Although FS does not significantly impact SMP, firms shouldn't rely solely on scale to influence market performance. Instead, attention to profitability and strategic board composition appears to yield stronger effects. Limitations and Further Considerations: While the high R^2 indicates strong explanatory power, further checks for potential overfitting or omitted variable bias could solidify confidence in these results.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis across descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and regression results reveals key insights into the relationships among stock market performance (SMP), Women on the Board (WB), Firm Leverage (FL), Firm Profitability (FP), and Firm Size (FS): Board Gender Diversity: The presence of women on boards (WB) is positively correlated with SMP and has a significant positive effect in the regression analysis, highlighting that gender-diverse boards tend to be associated with improved market performance. Leverage Management: FL shows a strong negative correlation with SMP and a significant negative regression coefficient, indicating that high leverage negatively impacts stock market performance, likely due to concerns about financial stability and debt risk. Profitability as a Key Factor: FP has the strongest positive correlation and regression impact on SMP, establishing it as the primary driver of market performance. High profitability significantly enhances firm valuation and investor confidence. Firm Size Considerations: FS does not show a significant relationship with SMP in the regression results, indicating that scale alone does not enhance market performance. This aligns with the correlation matrix, suggesting that firm growth strategies should focus on profitability and governance improvements rather than expansion alone.

Policy Recommendations: Encouraging Board Diversity: Policymakers should support initiatives for gender diversity in corporate boards, such as mandating or incentivizing a minimum percentage of female board members. This could improve governance practices, enhance firm decision-making, and, in turn, positively impact stock market performance. Debt and Financial Risk Regulations: Regulatory bodies may consider setting guidelines on acceptable leverage levels or establishing clearer disclosures for highly leveraged firms. This would help manage systemic risks associated with high corporate debt levels and improve transparency, allowing investors to make informed decisions. Profitability-Centric Governance: Given the positive relationship between profitability and SMP, regulatory agencies could emphasize profitability metrics as key indicators in financial disclosures. Providing a framework for reporting standardized profitability ratios would improve comparability and aid investors in assessing firms' market potential.

Practical Recommendations: Board Composition Strategy: Companies should consider increasing the representation of women on their boards as part of a broader governance improvement strategy. Enhanced diversity could drive more effective board decisions and better market perception. Optimizing Debt Structures: Firms should focus on optimizing their debt-to-equity ratios and carefully assess any additional leverage. Given the negative impact of high leverage on SMP, companies might benefit from debt-reducing debt or exploring alternative financing methods to reduce reliance on debt. Enhancing Profitability: Firms aiming to improve market

performance should prioritize profitability-enhancing strategies, such as operational efficiency, revenue diversification, and cost optimization. Maintaining high profitability ratios can drive investor confidence and ultimately boost stock market performance. Strategic Growth Beyond Scale: While firm size does not significantly impact SMP, growth strategies should focus on efficiency and governance rather than scale alone. Mergers, acquisitions, or expansions should be evaluated based on their potential to improve profitability and governance quality. In summary, the findings underscore that improving board diversity, carefully managing debt levels, and focusing on profitability are critical factors for enhancing stock market performance. These policies and strategies can guide firms and policymakers alike in fostering stable, high-performing markets.

References

- Abbas, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do creditors care about ESG performance? *International Journal of Management, Economics, and Social Sciences*, 13(5), 320-346.
- Abbas, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial statement fraud likelihood. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(2), 100365.
- Abdullahi, K., Musa, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Are CEOs hedge against share price fall? *Accounting and Business Research*, 53(5), 243-263.
- Abdullahi, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure. *Research in Management in Accounting*, 7(1), 221-252.
- Abubakar, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Which corporate owners are relevant in reducing earnings management? *Finance, Accounting, and Economic Insights*, 9(23), 16-75.
- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291-309.
- Adams, R. B., Haan, J., Terjesen, S. & Ees, H. (2015). Board diversity: Moving the field forward. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 23(2), 77-82.
- Adebowale, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of shareholder activism, on firm value. *Organisations and Markets in Emerging Economies*, 15(1)(4), 209-250.
- Adeleye, M., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The role of shareholders in controlling tax aggressiveness. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 62(3), 1140-1191.
- Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.
- Adeyemi, E., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of board financial expertise on earnings quality in Nigerian listed companies. *NDA Original Research Papers*, 2024-9(4), 1-30.
- Ahmed, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Unlocking the power of corporate governance and its impact on financial stability. *Governance and Management Review*, 9(1), 71-109.
- Ahmed, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Institutional and board ownership and corporate financial performance in Nigeria. *Advances in Business Research*, 14, 111-132.
- Ahmed, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). New insights on board structure and income smoothing hypothesis. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), 784-803.
- Alih, D. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board characteristics and cost of capital of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance, Business and Management Studies*, 4(2), 80-94.
- Amachukwu, V., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The moderating effect of board independence on CEO tenure and firm performance. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Analysis*, 9(27), 127-164.
- Amihud, Y., & Mendelson, H. (1986). Asset pricing and the bid-ask spread. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 17(2), 223-249.
- Andrew, L., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Estimating a predictive model for share price based on the influence of the board attributes in Nigeria. *Global Finance, Accounting, and Economics Perspectives*, 9(18), 590-620.
- Antonio, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). A corporate governance perspective on the audit committee and its role in improving earnings quality. *Advanced Research in Economics and Business Strategy*, 5(1), 78-107.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.
- Apochi, J. G., Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2024). The relationship between board diversity and CEO turnover. *Brazilian Business Review*, 3(2), 1-45.
- Arah, A. B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of SDGs on the socio-economic lives of people of Niger State. *Michigan Journal of Sustainability*, 12(1), 142-178.
- Audu, R. A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Audit committee attributes and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods

firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Management Sciences*, 3(3), 238-257.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(1), 423-433.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Determinants of environmental disclosure quality using Probit estimation among deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Warfare, Command and Capacity Building in Nigeria*. Archers.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Gender and nationality among board members and audit quality in Nigerian Listed Firms. *Audit and Accounting Review*, 3(1), 40-57.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The role of women in sustainability reporting. *Wayamba Journal of Management*, 14(1), 16-34.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Building a corporate governance index for an emerging market ESG performance. *University of Auckland Business Review*, 27(2), 81-117.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How women directors influence dividend policies? *Journal of Competition Law and Economics*, 20(2), 682-703.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of risk committee on sustainability disclosure. *Kardan Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 137-172.

Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Int Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.

Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria. *Intl Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.

Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.

Awolola, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality? *Journal of Financial Economics and Accounting*, 9(13), 784-821.

Awolola, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of environmental, social, and governance reporting on investment decisions. *Business, Management, and Economics Engineering*, 22(1), 66-106.

Baba, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management. *Accounting Education*, 32(4), 1-17.

Banz, R. W. (1981). The relationship between return and market value of common stocks. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 9(1), 3-18.

Bappa, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An analysis of the relationship between auditor independence and audit quality. *Universal Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(1), 32-55.

Bashir, I. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The effect of working capital management on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 46, 246-259.

Black, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Which ownership structure is significant in ESG performance? *American Business Review*, 27(2), 635-664.

Busayo, E., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do women enhance intellectual capital? *The Journal of Finance*, 74(4), 2902-2934.

Campbell, K., & Mínguez-Vera, A. (2008). Gender diversity in the boardroom and firm financial performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 83(3), 435-451.

Carter, D. A., Simkins, B. J., & Simpson, W. G. (2003). Corporate governance, board diversity, and firm value. *Financial Review*, 38(1), 33-53.

Charles, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of intellectual capital. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(2), 233-254.

Chordia, T., Roll, R., & Subrahmanyam, A. (2001). Market liquidity and trading activity. *Journal of Finance*, 56(2), 501-530.

Chuma, N., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of gender diversity on earnings management. *Asian American Research Journal*, 4(2024), 1-30.

Dania, I. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). CEO power and intangible assets. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 18(2), 270-286.

Ebiprewei, G., Yahaya, O. A., & Chukwueze, C. (2024). The asymmetric effects of integrated reports on firm value. *Journal of Governance and Integrity*, 7(1), 748-772.

Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (1992). The cross-section of expected stock returns. *Journal of Finance*, 47(2), 427-465.

Garba, M., Yahaya, O. A., & Ahmed, M. N. (2023). Firms characteristics and tax avoidance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria moderated by board gender. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 13(1), 1-20.

Gimbason, J. T., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Ownership structure and sustainability reporting. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 12(1), 77-102.

Gul, F. A., Srinidhi, B., & Ng, A. C. (2011). Board gender diversity and informational efficiency: Evidence from stock price synchronicity. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 51(3), 314-338.

- Gummi, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How does the heterogeneity of institutional investors affect audit quality? *Journal of Alternative Finance*, 1(2), 211-233.
- Hadi, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and accounting information asymmetry. *Asian Journal of Management Studies*, 3(3), 42-56.
- Haruna, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Foreign ownership and firm performance in the NGX 153 companies. *Korean Journal of Financial Studies*, 53(3), 392-437.
- Hassan, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An examination of the relationship between governance practices and financial reporting transparency. *International Journal of Management Technology and Engineering*, 14(5), 64-85.
- Ibrahim, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board demographic characteristics and cost of capital decisions. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting*, 5(2), 126-143.
- Ibrahim, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership structure and leverage. *The Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 17(4), 239-258.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Which nomination committee attributes matter in improving financial performance? *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(9), 231-257.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An inquiry into the nexus between a CEO and working capital management quality. *J of Smart Economic Growth*, 9(1), 135-163.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Applying GMM technique to auditor and value relationship. *Economic and Business*, 37, 247-274.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board of directors and financial statements fraud. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 12(1), 137-167.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Itopa, E., Imam, M., Musa, U., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Corporate governance and capital structure: Evidence from Nigeria listed financial services firms. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research (2602-3385)*, 3(12), 75-89.
- Kabir, Y. I., Tnushi, P. S., Jada, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership demographics and financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria moderated by firm size. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 13(3), 141-162.
- Lamidi, S., Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulwahab, A. I. (2024). Does board diversity influence a company's commitment to corporate social responsibility and sustainability initiatives? *Scientific Annals of Economics and Business*, 71(2), 315-349.
- Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 581-590.
- Lamido, I. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A meta-analysis of female directors and instability in firm value in Nigeria. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 11(7), 325-337.
- Lawal, C., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Could board financial expertise enhance audit quality? *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 23(2), 89-125.
- Lawal, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The role of firm complexity in the nexus between board size and financial performance. *European Management Journal*, 42, 288-298.
- Lawal, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on integrated reporting. *Management Decision*, 62(1), 370-392.
- Lawal, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). What drives the Nigerian leverage? *Annals of Economics and Finance*, 25(1), 345-385.
- Mironenkova, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of ownership type on firm performance in an emerging market. *Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 23(1), 250-294.
- Mohammed, S. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The intersection between ESG disclosure and audit committees. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, 70, 1-32.
- Moses, A., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Do boards care about biodiversity-related information disclosure? *Journal of Corporate Governance and Social Responsibility*, 10(21), 112-146.
- Muhammad, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of ESG performance disclosure. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 19(4), 123-140.
- Murtala, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Mgt and Technology*, 4(1), 35-51.
- Musa, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and firm value. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute Journal (Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 6(4), 204-220.
- Namadi, A., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Is there a positive correlation between board gender diversity and financial performance in publicly traded companies in Nigeria? *Accounting, Finance, and Economics Journal (ISSN: 3179-562X)*, 9(29), 132-164.
- Nasiru, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How effective is the risk committee in reducing corporate operating risk in Nigeria? *Journal of Management and Research*, 11(1), 26-54.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- Omotola, K., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The moderating effect of institutional ownership on board attributes and tax

aggressiveness. NDA Technical Papers, 2024-9(5), 1-40.

Onyabe, J. M., Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO and integrated reporting: Evidence from Africa listed communication services companies. *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 13(2), 86-99.

Pastor, L., & Stambaugh, R. F. (2003). Liquidity risk and expected stock returns. *Journal of Political Economy*, 111(3), 642-685.

Petroski, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). On the independence of the board and its committees, and earnings quality. *South East European University Review*, 19(1), 39-78.

Rahman, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Does it pay to be green? *Applied Economics*, 56(45), 5442-5469.

Rojas, G. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Women on boards and corporate social responsibility disclosure. *Revista de Métodos Cuantitativos para la Economía y la Empresa (Journal of Quantitative Methods for Economics and Business Administration)*, 37, 29-69.

Salihu, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Family ownership with asymmetric sustainability disclosure. *Business Research Quarterly*, 27(3), 346-375.

Salisu, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of female CEO on company leverage. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 34, 81-107.

Samaila, N., Suleiman, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate boards and leverage decisions. *Accounting Forum*, 47(2), 307-326

Samuel, F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Modelling and predicting corporate governance determinants of capital structure. *Dynamic Management Journal*, 8(2), 496-522.

Shittu, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The effect of institutional ownership on sustainability disclosure in emerging markets, Nigeria in perspective. *The Financial Economist: Accounting, Auditing, and Finance*, 9(19), 74-109.

Shokomi, L., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Sustainability committee and firm value. NDA Open Access Articles, 2024-9(3), 1-38.

Shuaibu, K., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and dividend policy. *Economics and Business Quarterly*, 6(3), 125-141.

Sulaiman, L., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and auditor choice. *South Asian Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 38-59.

Suleiman, T., Ladan, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do the sustainability committees matter in corporate financial performance? *Journal of Applied Economics and Business Studies*, 8(2), 23-64.

Suleiman, U., Popoola, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Equity financing and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Innovation and Social Science*, 6(12), 618-624.

Sumaila, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Could women directors reduce high leverage? *Journal of Sustainable Business and Economics and Finance*, 3(2), 17-42.

Terjesen, S., Sealy, R., & Singh, V. (2016). Board gender diversity: A comprehensive literature review and future research directions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 139(3), 333-352.

Tighil, M., Yahaya, O. A., Tauhid, S., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2024). The effects of board characteristics on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 17(1), 314-324.

Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.

Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 15(3), 393-410.

Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The impact of CEO female gender diversity and nationality on Internal Control System Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Int Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 50-61.

Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). CEO characteristics and corporate risk taking. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 14(1), 94-116.

Titman, S., & Wessels, R. (1988). The determinants of capital structure choice. *Journal of Finance*, 43(1), 1-19.

Tomasz, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The monitoring role of the CEO in enhancing audit quality. *Journal of Management and Financial Sciences*, 17(50), 120-150.

Umar, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and bankruptcy risk using GMM approach. *Applied Finance and Accounting*, 9(1), 242-256.

Usman, A., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Executive compensation and ESG performance. *International Journal of Sustainable Economics*, 10(26), 89-122.

Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria. *The Journal of Bus.*, 8(1), 36-47.

Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Do corporate governance mechanisms improve earnings? *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 16, 1-13.

Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The dynamics between a CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 30(1), 1-13.

- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Using binary regression analysis model to diagnose the effect of female directors on audit quality. *Reviews of Management Sciences*, 6(1), 70-89.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and credit ratings in Nigeria. *Int Journal of Economics, Management and Finance*, 2(1), 62-71.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Effect of board characteristics on firm value in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 47(1), 44-60.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The CEO power and sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. *J. of Business Mgt. and Accounting*, 13(7), 106-125.
- Vassalou, M., & Xing, Y. (2004). Default risk in equity returns. *Journal of Finance*, 59(2), 831-868.
- Welch, I. (2004). Capital structure and stock returns. *Journal of Political Economy*, 112(1), 106-131.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improve intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *J of Econ & Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An Application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity Influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Electronic payments system and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 5(20), 45-54.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2022). Can auditors reduce earnings management activities? *Review of Accounting and Finance (ISSN: 1475-7702)*, 22(4), 429-442.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43-75.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Finance*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Mgt Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamidi, Y. S. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.

- Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8, 269-275.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance & Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European J. of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). International financial reporting standards and earnings management behavior of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 7(18), 70-82.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M. & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Int Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: an empirical investigation using panel data. *Res J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *Journal of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). International financial reporting standards and value relevance of accounting information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics & Sustainable Dev.*, 6(12), 85-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). International financial reporting standards' adoption and financial statement effects: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(12), 107-122.
- Yakubu, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do board meetings and remuneration influence environmental disclosure? *Asian Review of Financial Research*, 37(2), 150-191.
- Yakubu, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and variability in integrated reporting gravity. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 8(50), 234-255.
- Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO attributes and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 112-124.
- Zhao, Y., Wang, W., & Zhang, X. (2018). Leverage and stock market performance: International evidence. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions & Money*, 55, 90-105.
- Zubairu, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of audit quality on financial reporting quality, mediated by audit committee effectiveness in Nigerian listed companies. *European Management Review*, 21(1), 1-22.
- Zumbiali, V., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do foreign and institutional ownerships enhance the quality of financial reports? NDA Working Paper Series Number 2024-8/26, 1-33.